

UNIVERSITY OF HAWAII AT MĀNOA

Institute for Astronomy

Pan-STARRS Project Management System

PS1 Design Reference Mission Pan-STARRS Telescope #1

Prepared For	: Pan-STARRS Management Office
Prepared By	: K. C. Chambers, Larry Denneau Jr.
Document No.	: PSDC-230-003-03
Document Date	: April 5, 2008
Revision	: 03

DISTRIBUTION STATEMENT

Approved for Public Release – Distribution is Unlimited

©Institute for Astronomy, University of Hawaii
2680 Woodlawn Drive, Honolulu, Hawaii 96822
An Equal Opportunity/Affirmative Action Institution

Submitted By:

[Insert Signature Block of Authorized Developer Representative]

Date

Approved By:

[Insert Signature Block of Customer Developer Representative]

Date

Revision History

Revision Number	Release Date	Description
00	2004-02-20	00 version release
01-DR	2007-03-01	01-DR version release
01	2007-03-31	01 version release
02	2008-03-31	02 version release
03	2008-04-01	03 version release

Contents

1	Referenced Documents	xi
1.1	Internal Documents	xi
1.2	External Documents	xi
2	Scope	1
2.1	Overview	1
2.2	The PS1 Science Mission Surveys	2
2.3	Document Overview	2
3	Constraints on the PS1 Design Reference Mission from the PS1 System and Site	3
3.1	Overview of some PS1 System Characteristics	3
3.2	PS1 Telescope	3
3.2.1	Mechanical Properties	3
3.2.2	Instrument Rotator and Cable Drape	4
3.2.3	PS1 Optical Design	5
3.2.4	PS1 Image Budget	5
3.2.5	Corrector coatings	6
3.2.6	Filter Set Properties	7
3.2.7	PS1 Bonn Shutter Properties	7
3.3	Environmental and Site Constraints	7
3.3.1	Site Parameters	7
3.3.2	Weather: Cloud Cover and Humidity	7
3.3.3	Atmospheric Seeing	8
3.3.4	Radio Frequency Interference at PS1	10
3.4	Geometrical Constraints	13
3.4.1	GPC1 Focal Plane	13
3.4.2	Observing Tessellation	13
3.5	Astronomical Constraints	13
3.5.1	Twilight	13
3.5.2	Lunar illumination	14
4	Estimated PS1 Sensitivities	14
5	PS1 Surveys	15
5.1	The 3π Steradian Survey	15
5.1.1	Calibration fields for 3π Survey	18
5.2	Medium Deep Survey	18
5.3	Solar System Sweet Spot Survey	19
5.4	Stellar Transit Survey	19
5.5	Deep Survey of M31	19
5.5.1	Microlensing in M31	19
5.6	Pan-STARRS Project Principal Investigator Discretionary Time	19
6	Survey Strategy	21

7	Implications of the Survey Strategy for exploration of the time domain	21
8	The PS1 Observing Scheduler	21
8.1	PS1 Scheduler Overview	22
8.2	Scheduler Concepts	22
8.3	Terminology	22
8.4	Configuration Files	22
8.5	Site Parameters	22
8.6	Telescope Parameters	23
8.7	Proposals	23
8.8	Pan-STARRS General Proposals	23
8.9	Pan-STARRS Medium-Deep Proposals	23
8.10	Pan-STARRS Calibration Proposals	23
8.11	A Pan-STARRS “Program”	24
8.12	Observation Scheduler	24
8.13	Sequences and Subsequences	24
8.14	Pan-STARRS Implementation of the PS1 Scheduler	24
8.15	3pi Region Modulation	24
9	Results from Simulation DRM1-v3 of the PS1 Design Reference Mission	25
9.1	Total Scheduling Performance	26
9.2	3pi and Sweetspots	27
9.3	Medium-Deep/STS/M31	27
9.4	Fidelity of the Scheduler	30
9.5	Summary of Scheduler Performance	30
10	Future Development of the PS1 Scheduler	30
10.1	Known Issues	30
10.2	Excess Idle Time	31
10.3	Look-Ahead	31
10.4	Baseline Schedule	31
10.5	Restartability	31
10.6	Real time Scheduling, Observing Tools, and Queue Operation	31
10.7	Engineering Requirements	31
10.8	Mitigation Strategy for Lost Observing Time	32
10.9	Release of Future Simulations of the PS1 DRM	32
11	Data Products, Management, and Access during the PS1 Science Mission	32
12	Public Data Release	32
13	Outreach	33
14	Acknowledgements	33
15	Appendix A: Table of PS1 Medium Deep Fields	33
16	Appendix B: PS1 STS and M31 Survey Fields	34

17 Appendix C: Table of PS1 Calibration Fields	34
18 Appendix D: Table of data sets to be provided on the web	35
19 Appendix E: RF Units and Conversions	36
20 Appendix F: Acronyms	36

List of Tables

1	The PS1 Mission Surveys	2
2	Summary of PS1 Characteristics	3
3	Telescope Parameters	4
4	PS1 Image Budget	6
5	Site Parameters	9
6	Compilation of Haleakala Seeing Measurements	9
7	Commercial and Institutional Sources of Radio Frequency Interference for PS1	12
8	Twilight per PS1 Filter	13
9	Allowable Lunar Illumination per PS1 Filter	14
10	PS1 Sensitivity Parameters	14
11	Estimated Sensitivities for the 3π Survey. The tabulated numbers use the above equations and assume 75 micron chips, aluminum coating, effective loss of 0.35 area from secondary mirror blockage and diffraction from baffles and secondary mirror support structure. The average sky brightness μ at Haleakala assumes the Wainscoat light pollution factor in g and r band, and an average air mass of 1.4 is assumed. The FWHM is taken to be 0.78 arcsec, or three pixels assuming OTA improvement. A read noise of 5 electrons rms is assumed, and an optimistic zero contribution from RFI.	17
12	Pessimistic Saturation Limits for 3π Survey Many brighter stars will be obtained in guide-star video mode. The pre-ucam ISP zeropoints are around 19, so with with the re-built ISP and ucam2, we expect the PS1 stellar catalog to have a dynamic range from 6th magnitude to the limiting magnitude of the 3π Survey.	17
13	Estimated PS1 Sensitivities for the Medium Deep Survey. The tabulated numbers use the same assumptions as those listed for the 3π Survey.	18
14	The PS1 Survey Cadences for perfect weather	20
15	The PS1 Rotator and Raster Strategy for PS1 Surveys	20
16	Overall Scheduling Efficiency	26
17	Individual Program-Filter Efficiencies	26
18	Medium-Deep/STS/M31 Summary	28
18	Medium-Deep/STS/M31 Summary	30
19	PS1 Medium Deep Fields	33
20	PS1 Deep M31 Survey and Stellar Transit Survey Fields	34
21	PS1 Calibration Fields	34
22	Complete set of PS1 Astrometric and Photometric Calibration Fields	35

List of Figures

1	Left: The PS1 Dome. Right: Graphic of Telescope showing the Lower Cassegrain Core with GPC1.	3
2	Northern (dark blue) and Southern (cyan) areas of the sky accessible with sky position angles of 180 and zero respectively. The sky is shown in a polar projection with the zenith at the center. The horizon is shown as a dark black circle. The grid lines are Hour Angle and Declination, with the black dot being the North Celestial Pole. On the left is the region accessible with a rotator range of 120 degrees. On the right is the same for a rotator range of 160 degrees. Note for a declination of 30 degrees north, the longest one can maintain a constant sky position angle is about 2 hours with a rotator range of 120. This becomes 4 hours for 160.	5
3	Eastern (yellow) and Western (magenta) areas of the sky accessible with a sky position angle of 270 and 90 degrees respectively. The sky is shown in the same projection and with the same grid as above. On the left is the region accessible with a rotator range of 120 degrees. On the right is the same for a rotator range of 160 degrees.	5
4	Overlay of Figure 1 and 2. "Union" regions can be observed in two orthogonal position angles. There is no choice of an orthogonal position angle for regions where there is no overlap, i.e where the color is the same as above. This illustrates some of the difficulties for scheduling that arise from a 120 rotator range constraint. On the left, if an object were first observed in the East at North 30, one would be forced to observe with a sky position angle of 270, as it is the only choice (if you want the pixels lined up N/E. Other options discussed below.) Then as little as half an hour later, you can not return to the same orientation, but must go to an orthogonal orientation. For at least the first year of the PS1 Mission, as discussed below, it is preferred to have observations of the same field, separated by a TTI, to be in the same exact orientation (because there is no existing static sky first time around.) Now, you can pick any orientation, i.e not line up N/E, but this just "warps" the above diagrams about zenith. The end result is the same: observations have to be exquisitely timed to get re-visits at the same orientation. This is a huge constraint on the schedule, and although it is not yet proved, adding this constraint appears to over constrain the scheduling to the point where the mission is no longer schedulable.	5
5	PS1 Telescope Non-ADC Optical Design This is the "as-built" optical design with a thick L1 corrector replacing the planned but non-existing Atmospheric Dispersion Corrector or ADC.	6
6	The Lower Cass Core (LCC) showing L1 and L2 correctors, 3 stacked filter slides, and GPC Camera.	6
7	Left: Model of broadband anti-reflection coating for PS1 corrector optics. Right: Reflectivity of protected silver, expected for new PS1 M2a secondary mirror.	7
8	g Filter	7
9	r Filter	7
10	i Filter	8
11	z Filter	8
12	y Filter	8
13	Shutter Properties. Shutter parameters, shutter test characteristics, and schematic shutter velocity profile.	9
14	Haleakala wind distribution. The radial axis corresponds to wind speed in units of m/sec. The azimuthal axis corresponds to wind direction. The intensity of the plot indicates the number of data points at a given combination of wind speed and direction. The deficit of data points to the north is an instrumental effect. From Bradley et al, 2006.	9
15	Left: High, median, and low nighttime temperature on Haleakala over the course of a year. Right, average nighttime relative humidity over the course of a year. From KCE Environmental.	9

16	Left: Haleakala average cloud cover as a function of time of day. Blue is clear, Green is partly cloudy, Yellow is mostly cloudy, and Red is overcast. Note the nighttime is naturally much better than the daytime. These measurements suggest an average of 11 hours of "Clear" time for 50 percent of the nights. It is not clear how sensitive this data is to high cirrus. Right: the altitude of the boundary layer as determined by the CAPS system. This is relevant to the night sky brightness, see text. From KCE Environmental.	9
17	Haleakala Seeing, as measured by Zirkind in 1965 with Baker-Nunn Camera. these are the most optimistic values, but were measured at a focal plane rather than by differential image motion. . . .	9
18	Haleakala Seeing, R_0 versus time (Hawaii Standard Time) measured with the ATST DIMM on ATST Tower (about the height and isolation of PS1). This suggests there is 11 hours per night with median seeing less than or equal to 0.78 arcseconds, or 3 OTA pixels. (Night sky brightness is a separate issue, see the Section on twilight and length of night.) These are the most optimistic DIMM measurements made on Haleakala, see the Seeing Table for comparison.	10
19	Radio Spectrum as observed outside on the roof of the PS1 Support Building. The x-axis is linear in units of MHz, from 0 to 500 MHz, with vertical lines every 50 MHz. The y-axis is in decibels, it is equivalent to a logarithmic scale covering 8 decades, ranging from $10^{-8}mW$ to $1mW$. In the US, the band from 225 to 400 MHz is for exclusive use of the US government for fixed and satellite transmitters. There are certainly a number of detected transmissions in this band. See Appendix D. The observed radio spectrum is currently being monitored and archived 24 hours a day.	11
20	Right: the 3 degree field of view of PS1 with an inscribed hexagon of 5.84 square degrees. Left: Outside view of the celestial sky tessellated into 6252 fields. Of these fields, 5464 have boresight centers ≥ -30 degrees Declination.	13
21	PS1 Throughput.	14
22	PS1 Survey Strategy. The colored boxes represent sections of the sky in a "mercator-like" rectangular projection - it shows the sky from $-30 \leq \delta \leq 90$, and each colored box represents approximately 2 hours in Right Ascension or 30 degrees at the equator in this projection. Going down the the staircase is in the time direction, with each step a step approximately once per lunation, and shifting constantly to the East as the year progresses. After one year, the survey is back where it started from on the sky. The center of each observed region is approximately at Solar opposition at new moon. This is schematic. In the detailed schedule the size of each region must be longer in the winter and shorter in the summer by more than 10 percent to account for the change in the length of the night. Further adjustments to the scheduling are required to match the synodic lunar period with the annual sidereal period.	21
23	Detailed survey strategy within a lunation, showing the approximate filter balance and area coverage.	21
24	Graphical description of scheduler observation windowing.	24
25	Haleakala night lengths over one year.	25
26	3pi survey coverage for observing cycle 89 (01-3piR-2007 through 30-3piR-2007). Note that the central 3pi region is slightly off-center due to region modulation described in Section 8.15.	25
27	Sweetspot survey coverage for observing cycle 89 (01-3piR-2007 through 30-3piR-2007).	25
28	Example of results of simulation for scheduling of individual nights. These are night 58, 59, and 62 of the mission, showing a range of how the scheduler coped with the weather. THE solid thin line indicates the opacity from the cloud detector. If the line has three possible levels, LOW, indicating clear or "photometric" sky, MEDIUM, or partly cloudy (at least 3/5 of sky is clear), and HIGH, which means overcast. Plotted simultaneously as small triangles is the humidity. If the humidity exceeds 90 percent the Observatory closes and stays closed until the humidity has been below 90 percent for one half hour. Along the top, color coded are the observations and programs and filters scheduled. Black is No Observing, Grey is Idle, which means the scheduler could not figure out what to do: its ability to schedule anything was overconstrained,	27

29	More individual nights. Nights 63, 64, and 65 of the simulation. Same caption as Figure 28.	27
30	3pi pair completion. Six Observing Cycles (lunations)	27
31	3pi pair completion. Six Observing Cycles (lunations)	29
32	3pi and Sweetspot TTI pair completion.	29
33	Position of all special fields to be used as Calibration fields. Red, Medium Deep Survey Fields, Black Calibration Fields, Orange, M31, Blue, STS Campaign.	34

1 Referenced Documents

1.1 Internal Documents

Reference	Title
PSDC-230-001-01	PS1 Science Goals Statement
PSDC-230-002-00	PS1 Mission Concept Statement
PSDC-230-003-00	PS1 Design Reference Mission (Superseded by this document)
PSDC-230-004-DR	PS1 System Subsystem Specification (PS1 Requirements)
PSDC-230-005-DR	PS1 Plan of Operations
PSDC-220-001-00	PS1 Science Consortium Polices
PSDC-330-004-01	The PS1 Telescope Non-ADC Optical Design
PSDC-330-002-00	The Pan-STARRS Filter Set Specifications
PSDC-330-010-00	PS1 Shutter: a Bonn Shutter for PS1
PSDC-800-003-00	The PS1 Telescope Scheduler, Larry Denneau Jr.
PS Memorandum	Effects of RF Transmission on Optical CCD Systems

1.2 External Documents

Reference	Title
1839 EIG-EMC-94-45	Electromagnetic Compatibility Survey, Advanced Electro-Optical System Summary
AFRL-DE-PS-TR-1998-1040	Summary of Electromagnetic Interference Measurements at Haleakala Observatories
Bradley et. al. 2006	PASP 118, 172
Zirkind 1965	Applied Optics 4, 1077

2 Scope

The purpose of the PS1 Design Reference Mission (DRM) is to establish the baseline plan for the PS1 Science Mission against which the Science Mission as executed will be measured. The DRM is to be a detailed, realistic, schedulable description of the PS1 Science Mission, consistent with the PS1 Science Goals Statement, PS1 Mission Concept Statement, and the PS1 System Subsystem Specifications (the "Requirements").

Some important factual items that impact the accuracy of the predicted performance of the PS1 System are still unknown at the time of this version of the DRM. These include, but are not limited to: the current night sky brightness given recent and planned the local light pollution mitigation procedures; the contribution to the read noise of the detector due to Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) after removal of the commercial broadcast towers from Haleakala and after the implementation of a variety of concepts for RFI mitigation have been implemented; and the actual image quality and seeing distribution expected from the site, telescope, and camera system.

All of these factors will be better understood after some combination of commissioning with the TC3 Camera and the GPC1 Camera itself. If necessary a revised DRM based on new information obtained between the date of this publication and ORR could potentially require some modifications to the baseline mission described herein.

2.1 Overview

PS1 is a research and development project built as a prototype for the Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System or Pan-STARRS project. The Pan-STARRS project expects to build "PS4", a System with 4 times the collecting area of PS1 and with four 1.4 Gigapixel OTA cameras.

The primary science design drivers for PS1 from the PS1 Mission Goals Statement are:

- Precision photometric and astrometric survey of stars in the Milky Way and the Local Group;
- Surveying our Solar System, including searching for Potentially Hazardous Objects among Near Earth Asteroids;
- New constraints on Dark Energy and Dark Matter;
- Exploration and categorization of the astrophysical time domain, including, but not limited to, explosive transients, microlensing events in M31, and a transit search for exo-planets; and
- Providing a development platform for prototyping PS4 components, subsystems, and survey strategy.

These goals drive the design and engineering requirements, but do not begin to cover the vast array of solar system, galactic, extragalactic, and cosmological studies that can be done with the PS1 data products.

The vision of the PS1 System and the PS1SC that is reflected in the Design Reference Mission was described at the first PS1 Science Consortium Science Council Meeting: (i) the Key Science Project teams are scientific collaborations beyond collecting the PS1 data described in the surveys below, they extend to coordinated follow-up observations across key project teams; (ii) the Science Council as a whole is a scientific collaboration that works together on common goals of data analysis of the PS1 Surveys; (iii) the PS1 System, and the Design Reference Mission built on the capabilities of that System establish a new paradigm for 21st Century ground based optical astronomy: a integrated system from coordinated observations, to metadata, to data reduction and analysis, to the scientific understanding of the collection of detections and non-detections, and their selection functions, into scientific discoveries from earth impactors to the edge of the universe.

Table 1. The PS1 Mission Surveys

PS1 Surveys	Filters	Percent Time
3 π Steradian Survey	g, r, i, z, y	56
Calibration Fields	g, r, i, z, y	2
Medium Deep Survey	g, r, i, z, y	25
Solar System Sweet Spot Survey	r	5
Stellar Transit Survey	i	4
Deep Survey of M31	g, r, i, z, y	2
Principal Investigator Discretionary Time		6

The PS1 System could be seen as an observatory and data archive. However, The PS1 Science Mission as established in the PS1 Mission Concept Statement, and refined, although not finalized, in this iteration of the Design Reference Mission, is fundamentally designed around the notion that the PS1 System, including Science Analysis Clients, is an integrated science-goal driven machine with quantitative quality assurance and investigation and control of systematic errors for the good of union of the key science project goals.

2.2 The PS1 Science Mission Surveys

The PS1 Science Mission is composed of the PS1 Surveys and their relative observing time distribution shown in Table 1.

As put forth in the PS1 Mission Goals Statement, PS1 wishes to maximize the scientific output of PS1. The Mission Goals are diverse, and require a sophisticated strategy in terms of cadencing, duration, and revisits, filter choice and lunar illumination, and weather in order to attempt some optimization of the observing schedule that will meeting the Science Goals of all the Key Science Areas. Simulations show that increasing diversity in the survey strategies lead to increasing inefficient observing schedules and diminished returns. It is hoped that this document fully explains the choices involved and the baseline strategy chosen which defined the observing plan that, given the vagaries of weather and downtime, the actual observations will be sufficiently close to meeting so as the Science Mission is deemed successful.

2.3 Document Overview

In this PS1 Mission Concept Survey we detail the system sensitivities, and an overview of the PS1 Surveys as currently envisioned in order to meet the PS1 Mission Goals Statement. The PS1 Mission Concept has gone through a large number of iterations with the intent of optimizing the overall scientific return for the the PS1 Mission Science Goals. There are many competing aspects to this, and no one Mission Concept will uniformly satisfy all science goals, but the results of our preliminary research so far suggest we have found something close to an optimum Conceptual Survey. The full details and comparisons with alternative suggested strategies will be presented in the PS1 Design Reference Mission. This shorter document is to inform the PS Project and PS1 Science Consortium of the current status of our research on finding a nearly optimal solution for maximizing the science goals of participants in the PS1 Science Consortium.

The current PS1 Mission concept is based on a limited set of simulations with our modified version of the LSST simulator, and hand calculations. The PS1 DRM will present detailed results of these simulations. We are developing related interactive code for real time scheduling and computer assisted scheduling for PS1. Fully automated scheduling is not a requirement for PS1.

Table 2. Summary of PS1 Characteristics

Characteristic	Quantity
Focal Length	8000 mm
Plate Scale	38.8 mm/radian
Pixel size	10 μ m
Pixel size	0.263 arcseconds
Total Field of view	3.0 degree diameter circle
Total Field of view	7.068 square degrees
Primary mirror	1800 mm diameter, protected aluminum coating
Secondary mirror	947 mm diameter, protected silver coating
f/number	f/4.44
Effective aperture	$0.65 \times \pi 92^2 \text{ cm}^2 = 17284 \text{ cm}^2$ including diffraction and obscuration losses
Camera fill factor	90%: 9% from internal streets, 2.5% from external gaps, 2.5% from dead cells
Other losses	1 to 2 percent for streak removal of objects inside geosynchronous orbit

3 Constraints on the PS1 Design Reference Mission from the PS1 System and Site

3.1 Overview of some PS1 System Characteristics

The PS1 field of view with good image quality is 3 degrees in diameter. the 1.44 Gigapixel camera fills this circular FOV and more, with detectors outside the 3 degree circle for WFS and optimization of overlapping regions. The basic characteristics of the PS1 System are listed in Table 2.

3.2 PS1 Telescope

3.2.1 Mechanical Properties

The PS1 Telescope is an alt-az telescope with an instrument rotator built by EOST with an enclosure built by EOS. In order for the telescope fork to accommodate the "Lower Cassegrain Core" or LCC, which is mounted on the rotator and includes the Filter Mechanism, Shutter, and GPC1 Camera, the EOST 2.2 meter telescope mount was used, even though the PS1 mirror is 1.8 meters.

The PS1 Dome motion closely follows the telescope through a featherweight direct coupling.

The dome has four independently commandable vents for air flow through the dome. The dome slit shutters, consist of two independently commandable shutters that can be both be deployed over the top on to the back side of the dome, or one can be use for a wind shield.

Some of the mechanical properties of the PS1 Telescope are given in Table 3. These are also input values to the PS1 Mission simulator discussed below.

Other important properties of the PS1 telescope include that fact that the Secondary Mirror is mounted on a hexapod and can be moved in five axes: x,y,z,tip, tilt. The Primary Mirror is on a pneumatic support system and can be commanded y,z, tip, and tilt. The Primary Mirror can be moved in the x direction as well, but this is not on a powered actuator, but must be done manually. Furthermore the Primary Mirror has a 12 point astigmatic correction system. Thus there are 22 independent mirror actuators that can be use to bring the optics into proper collimation, alignment with the optical axis as defined by the axis of the instrument rotator, and in addition allow for modest amounts of Primary mirror deformation to remove trefoil, coma, and astigmatism Wave front sensing is required to bring the telescope into proper focus, alignment,

Figure 1 Left: The PS1 Dome. Right: Graphic of Telescope showing the Lower Cassegrain Core with GPC1.

collimation, and these higher order optical corrections. The GPC1 Camera will have both a deployable Shack-Hartmann device for deriving a system matrix for the optical mirror motions, and modeling them as a function of elevation and truss and mirror temperature. This can not be used in conjunction with normal GPC imaging. The GPC1 camera will have Curvature wavefront sensing outside the 3 degree diameter quality field of view for continuous wave-front sensing and mirror position correction.

3.2.2 Instrument Rotator and Cable Drape

Due to the substantial amount of cabling to the GPC1 Camera on the Instrument Rotator of the PS1 telescope, the cables do not go through a regular cable wrap. Instead a "cable drape" is being implemented. The Cable Drape limits the range of the instrument rotator. Under the current design, the cable drape has a range of 120 degrees.

Detailed investigation has shown that this restriction of rotator range may have a significant impact on both goals of the PS1 Science Mission and scheduling of the PS1 Science Mission.

On the other hand, if the cable drape design could be modified to be extended to have a range of at least 160 degrees, this would mitigate most of the impact.

This is illustrated and discussed in Figures 2, 3, and 4.

3.2.3 PS1 Optical Design

The PS1 telescope is a Cassegrain design with a three element corrector, 10 mm filters, and a circular 3.0 degree full field of view. Figure 5 shows a schematic. The primary and secondary mirrors are labeled as M1 and M2, and the refractive corrector optics are labeled as L1, L2, and L3, where L3 is the entrance window of the CCD dewar window.

Table 3. Telescope Parameters

Parameter	Description	Value
DomAlt_MaxSpeed	Dome alt max speed, degrees/second	2.0
DomAlt_Accel	Dome alt acceleration, degrees/second ²	1.5
DomAlt_Decel	Dome alt deceleration, degrees/second ²	1.5
DomAz_MaxSpeed	Dome azimuth max speed, degrees/second	3.0
DomAz_Accel	Dome azimuth acceleration, degrees/second ²	1.27
DomAz_Decel	Dome azimuth deceleration, degrees/second ²	1.27
TelAlt_MaxSpeed	Telescope alt max speed, degrees/second	2.0
TelAlt_Accel	Telescope alt acceleration, degrees/second ²	1.5
TelAlt_Decel	Telescope alt deceleration, degrees/second ²	1.5
TelAz_MaxSpeed	Telescope azimuth max speed, degrees/second	2.0
TelAz_Accel	Telescope azimuth acceleration, degrees/second ²	1.5
TelAz_Decel	Telescope azimuth deceleration, degrees/second ²	1.5
Rotator_MaxSpeed	Rotator max speed, degrees/second	1.86
Rotator_Accel	Rotator deceleration, degrees/second ²	0.50
Rotator_Decel	Rotator deceleration, degrees/second ²	0.50
TelAz_MinPos	Telescope AZ absolute min position, degrees	-120
TelAz_MaxPos	Telescope AZ absolute max position, degrees	320
Rotator_MinPos	Rotator AZ absolute min position, degrees	-60 (TBR)
Rotator_MaxPos	Rotator AZ absolute max position, degrees	+60 (TBR)
Filter_MoveTime	Time in seconds to change between loaded filters	30.
Settle_Time	General system settle time, in seconds	5 (TBR)

Figure 2 Northern (dark blue) and Southern (cyan) areas of the sky accessible with sky position angles of 180 and zero respectively. The sky is shown in a polar projection with the zenith at the center. The horizon is shown as a dark black circle. The grid lines are Hour Angle and Declination, with the black dot being the North Celestial Pole. On the left is the region accessible with a rotator range of 120 degrees. On the right is the same for a rotator range of 160 degrees. Note for a declination of 30 degrees north, the longest one can maintain a constant sky position angle is about 2 hours with a rotator range of 120. This becomes 4 hours for 160.

Figure 3 Eastern (yellow and Western (magenta) areas of the sky accessible with a sky position angle of 270 and 90 degrees respectively. The sky is shown in the same projection and with the same grid as above. On the left is the region accessible with a rotator range of 120 degrees. On the right is the same for a rotator range of 160 degrees.

Figure 4 Overlay of Figure 1 and 2. "Union" regions can be observed in two orthogonal position angles. There is no choice of an orthogonal position angle for regions where there is no overlap, i.e where the color is the same as above. This illustrates some of the difficulties for scheduling that arise from a 120 rotator range constraint. On the left, if an object were first observed in the East at North 30, one would be force to observe with a sky position angle of 270, as it is the only choice (if you want the pixels lined up N/E. Other options discussed below.) Then as little as half an hour later, you can not return to the same orientation, but must go to an orthogonal orientation. For at least the first year of the PS1 Mission, as discussed below, it is preferred to have observations of the same field, separated by a TTI, to be in the same exact orientation (because there is no existing static sky first time around.) Now, you can pick any orientation, i.e not line up N/E, but this just "warps" the above diagrams about zenith. The end result is the same: observations have to be exquisitely timed to get re-visits at the same orientation. This is a huge constraint on the schedule, and although it is not yet proved, adding this constrains appears to over constrain the scheduling to the point where the mission is no longer schedulable.

Figure 5 PS1 Telescope Non-ADC Optical Design This is the "as-built" optical design with a thick L1 corrector replacing the planned but non-existing Atmospheric Dispersion Corrector or ADC.

This design requires the presence of filters to achieve proper focus. The filter mechanism will have 3 layers of filters, 2 filters per layer, but only one filter will be in the optical path at any given time. Examples are labeled as F1, F2, and F3.

By specification the PS1 telescope has a focal length of 8000 mm, so the plate scale is $38 \mu\text{m}/\text{arcsecond}$. GPC1 Camera has 10 micron pixels, so the side of a pixel is 0.263 arcseconds. The focal plane is not flat, but has a (ADC optimized) convex radius of curvature of $4.7 \times 10^5 \text{ mm}$.

The details of the design of the PS1 telescope are given in PSDC-330-004-01, "The PS1 Telescope Non-ADC Optical Design" and references therein. This design was derived by Ed Mannery from an initial optical design by Klaus Hodapp. The optical layout is available as a Zeemax design file NOADC-M-1.0ZMX, which will be put on the www.ps1sc.org web site.

Figure 6 The Lower Cass Core (LCC) showing L1 and L2 correctors, 3 stacked filter slides, and GPC Camera.

Table 4. PS1 Image Budget

Source	FWHM arcsec zenith	FWHM arcsec 70 degree	R_o cm zenith	R_o cm 70 degree
Site Seeing	0.90(TBR)	1.71	11.22	5.89
Telescope	0.40	0.76	25.26	13.26
Camera	0.33	0.33	30.99	30.99
IPP	0.15	0.15	67.41	67.41
Total (quadrature)	1.05	1.91	79.17	75.60

3.2.4 PS1 Image Budget

The PS1 Image Budget from the PS1 System Subsystem Specifications is reproduced in 4.

Table 4 shows the maximum allowable contributions towards the image point spread function (PSF) from the Site Seeing, the PS1 Telescope, Camera, and Image Processing Pipeline subsystems. These contributions are expressed in three different units and at two different zenith angles, $z = 0^\circ$ and $z = 70^\circ$. The total is the sum, added in quadrature of these contributions.

Table 4 shows the maximum allowable contributions towards the image point spread function (PSF) from the Site Seeing, the PS1 Telescope, (dominated by collimation, alignment, and higher order optical distortion terms of the thin primary mirror) Camera, (dominated by physical size of pixels, charge diffusion, and deviations from the spherical focal surface), and IPP (dominated by numerical pixel representation considerations). The FWHM is given in arcseconds, and the two columns are for the telescope at zenith and at a zenith angle of 70 degrees.

The last two columns show the equivalent contributions in terms of the Fried parameter, R_0 . See the PS1 System Subsystem Specification for more details. The conversion between the two is

$$\text{FWHM} = 2.02 \times 10^5 \frac{\lambda}{R_0} \quad (1)$$

where it is assumed above that R_0 and λ are in the same units, that FWHM is in arcseconds, and that σ is in μm . For $\lambda = 500 \text{ nm}$, this becomes

$$\text{FWHM} = \frac{10.1}{R_0} \quad (2)$$

It is assumed in 4 that the seeing scales with zenith angle according to the equation $(R_0)_z = (R_0)_{z=0} \times \cos^{\frac{3}{5}} z$, whereas the variation in telescope image size as a function of zenith angle is an estimate due to flexure.

The contribution from the Site Seeing may be pessimistic, see the Section 3.5 below. Contributions from the dome have not been separately accounted for in this discussion. Empirically we can determine optimum venting, shutter, and wind orientation effects. The dome and mirror are cooled during the day, kept at the anticipated temperature at midnight.

3.2.5 Corrector coatings

The optical design of the PS1 Telescope includes three lenses with 6 air/glass interfaces. Measured reflectivities are not yet available. It is hard to have less than 0.5 percent reflectivity from 400nm to 1.04 microns. A design model by Geza Keller is shown in Figure 7 A study of ghost image analysis is provided in "Preliminary Design of the Pan-STARRS Telescope Optics".

Figure 7 Left: Model of broadband anti-reflection coating for PS1 corrector optics. Right: Reflectivity of protected silver, expected for new PS1 M2a secondary mirror.

3.2.6 Filter Set Properties

The PS1 Filter Set, manufactured by Barr Incorporated, are made of synthetic fused silica with flat parallel surfaces and an octagon shape. See "The Pan-STARRS Filter Set Specifications" for details. The transmission, reflectance, and out of band transmission are shown in Figures 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12. Note that the transmission varies across the filter (particularly in the g filter) and as a function of the angle of incidence, which is important for the f/4.4 beam. Numerical tabulations of these curves will be made available on www.ps1sc.org.

3.2.7 PS1 Bonn Shutter Properties

The PS1 Camera Shutter, built by the University of Bonn is a slit type shutter with a square aperture of 480 mm × 480 mm. It is an impact free, low acceleration device. Instead of driving the shutter blades at high speed/acceleration the ≤ 1 msec timing accuracy is achieved by the simple yet very precise motion control of both blades.

The shutter is controlled by a TTL signal from the Camera. The timing accuracy is better than 1 msec across the aperture. See Figure 13. The shutter blade movements during an open or close command follow a well determined velocity profile which is identical for both blades and both movement directions. This is illustrated in the schematic of the velocity profile Figure 13. The measured PS1 shutter velocity profile will be available on the www.ps1sc.org website.

See "The PS1 Shutter, a Bonn Shutter for the Pan-STARRS Prototype Telescope 1" for details.

3.3 Environmental and Site Constraints

3.3.1 Site Parameters

Basic parameters of the PS1 Site are given in Table 5.

Figure 8 g Filter

Figure 9 r Filter

Figure 10 i Filter

Figure 11 z Filter

Pan-STARRS, 21" Octagon "y2" band filter

Figure 12 y Filter

Table 5. Site Parameters

Parameter	Description	Value
Hawaiian Standard Time	Offset in hours from UT	-10
latitude	PS1 latitude	+20 42 25.558
longitude	PS1 east longitude	203 44 38.740
height	PS1 altitude, meters	3067.965 (TBR)
pressure	Mean Site atmospheric pressure	710 millibars (TBR)
temperature	Mean Site night temperature	7 degrees Celsius (TBR)

Shutter type	Slit-type shutter with two independent blades driven by stepper motors.
Weight ShMU	27 kg
Weight ShCU	6 kg
Aperture size	480mm x 480mm
Minimum exposure time	2msec.
Exposure time error	< 1msec.
Exposure inhomogeneity	+200µsec over the full field of view.
Repetition rate	The minimum time interval between start of consecutive exposures is (exposure time + 0.02sec).

Ref.	Item	Requirement	Test result	Sect.
3.3.6.1	Shortest exposure time	100ms	2ms	5, p. 4
	longest exposure time	300s	any (by design)	
3.3.6.2	exposure accuracy	< 0.5% @2s (i.e. < 10ms)	1ms	6.2
3.3.6.5	Dead time	< 1.0s	0.92s	
3.3.6.7	Clear aperture	480mm	480mm	
3.3.6.8	Blade position = f(time)	10ms accur.	see Table 3	12
3.3.6.9	MTBF	> 480000	we expect > 10 ⁸	8
3.3.6.10	Volume	< 51mm(H) > < 1855mm(W) > < 750mm(L)	50mm(H) > 1692mm(W) > 632mm(L)	
3.3.6.11	Weight	< 32Kg	27Kg	
3.3.6.12	Torque on rotator	< 6.78Nm	1.2Nm to 3.6Nm	9
3.3.6.13	Heat dissipation	< 0.4W	< 0.4W	10
3.3.6.15	Modularity	quick disconnect cable	o.k.	see [5]
	Light-tightness	< 30phot/s/pix @room light	4 10 ⁻² phot/s/pix @day-light	11
	Air-tightness	gasket seals	o.k.	see [5]

Figure 13 Shutter Properties. Shutter parameters, shutter test characteristics, and schematic shutter velocity profile.

Figure 14 Haleakala wind distribution. The radial axis corresponds to wind speed in units of m/sec. The azimuthal axis corresponds to wind direction. The intensity of the plot indicates the number of data points at a given combination of wind speed and direction. The deficit of data points to the north is an instrumental effect. From Bradley et al, 2006.

3.3.2 Weather: Cloud Cover and Humidity

On average, 35% of the nights on Haleakala are photometric, and an additional 30 percent are useable with either very low extinction or more than 60% of the sky clear of clouds as shown by the IR cloud camera.

The wind distribution on Haleakala from Bradley et al, 2006 is shown in Figure 14. The wind is predominately from east-northeast, i.e from the direction of the Haleakala Crater. PS1 is in the wake of the flow into the wall of the crater.

Figure 15 shows the yearly temperature and humidity trends.

Figure 16 shows average cloud distribution over a night. Blue is clear, Green is partly cloudy, Yellow is mostly cloudy, and Red is overcast. Note the nighttime is naturally much better than the daytime. These measurements suggest 11 hours of "Clear" time for 50 percent of the nights. It is not clear that this data is sensitive to high cirrus.

Figure 16 also shows the distribution of nights with the boundary layer (as determined by the CAPS system) at a given altitude. This is important as when the boundary layer is between 5000 and 9000 feet (above MSL) this means the clouds are well below the summit, and actually helping the night sky brightness by blocking out the lights from inhabited areas of Maui. When the boundary layer reaches 10,000 feet, the summit is in clouds and fog, and from this plot this occurs, on average, 120 nights of the year.

3.3.3 Atmospheric Seeing

The night time seeing at Haleakala Observatories has not been well characterized. The site has predominately use for solar observations and satellite tracking and imaging applications, neither of which provides information relevant to night time observing with PS1.

Figure 15 Left: High, median, and low nighttime temperature on Haleakala over the course of a year. Right, average nighttime relative humidity over the course of a year. From KCE Environmental.

Figure 16 Left: Haleakala average cloud cover as a function of time of day. Blue is clear, Green is partly cloudy, Yellow is mostly cloudy, and Red is overcast. Note the nighttime is naturally much better than the daytime. These measurements suggest an average of 11 hours of "Clear" time for 50 percent of the nights. It is not clear how sensitive this data is to high cirrus. Right: the altitude of the boundary layer as determined by the CAPS system. This is relevant to the night sky brightness, see text. From KCE Environmental.

Table 6. Compilation of Haleakala Seeing Measurements

Name	Date	Measured R_0 cm	Calc R_0 cm	Measured FWHM arcsec	Calculated FWHM arcsec	Technique	Comment
Zirkind	1965		28 ± 14	$0.36^{1.3}_{0.24}$		Star trails	Baker-Nunn Camera
Bradley et al	2006	14.7 ± 6.3			0.69	DIMM	
Chun	2005	14.8			0.68	DIMM	on AGL Bldg Jan-Oct
Chun	2005	11.2			0.90	DIMM	on AGL Bldg Jan-Dec
ATST-Tower	2005	13			0.72	DIMM	for 5 hours before midnight
ATST-Tower	2005	17			0.78	DIMM	for 7 hours after midnight
MAGNUM	2006		10.1	1.0		Images/Logs	no venting, low dome

Extensive DIMM measurements have been made. The DIMM on roof of the AGL Building occasionally showed a distribution that was not "log-norm" with an excess of data points at low r_0 values. This has never been explained. The very low r_0 values would suggest seeing of several arcseconds, and values this large have not been observed by an imaging system.

Note the total Chun data set, which had three months of unusually bad weather, gave a median value of 0.9 arcseconds FWHM. This was the value quoted by Wainscoat, and is the value adopted in the PS1 SSS Image budget, see 4. Thus the image quality required to meet the PS1 spec, as measured by the FWHM measured in a detrended PS1 image, is 1.05 arcseconds at zenith (unobservable with alt-az mount) and 1.91 arcseconds at zenith angle of 70 degrees (geometric airmass approximately 2.9). Thus PS1 Scientists should plan for the System to meet this specification.

However, there is reason to be optimistic, although one should not depend on it. The ATST DIMM site is on a tower with a location and height more comparable to the PS1 telescope, and gives a median seeing (evening) of 0.78 arcseconds. This happens to be 3 pixels per FWHM, the optimum for OTA shifting. With OTA shifting we may be able to remove some of the non-optics aspects of seeing that contribute to image quality, such as dome and telescope shake. Hence this is the value used in the PS1 Survey Sensitivities Tables below.

Measurements are given in Figure 17, Figure 18 and in Table 6.

3.3.4 Radio Frequency Interference at PS1

Radio transmitters within and adjacent to Haleakala Observatories seriously degrade the astronomical quality of the site. The International Astronomical Union (IAU) has determined that the acceptable level of RFI as measured outside an observatory doing optical or infrared observations should be less than $2 \mu W/m^2$ (integrated over the radio spectrum).

Currently various locations within the Haleakala Observatories exceed $184,000 \mu W/m^2$ and levels exceeding $60,000 \mu W/m^2$ are measured nearly everywhere within the Observatory grounds. See Figure 19 for an observed radio spectrum at PS1, taken with the PS1 radio frequency spectrum analyzer. Table 7 has a list of known transmitters, their properties and status. Column six In Table 7, lists the E-Field measured at the Air Glow Building (AGR), which is the nearest to the present PS1 Site. These measurements are compiled from two studies, 1839 EIG-EMC-94-45, "Electromagnetic Compatibility Survey, Advanced Electro-Optical System", 1994, and AFRL-DE-PS-IR-1998, "Summary of Electromagnetic Interference Measurements at Mt. Haleakala Observation Facilities", Lawry et al, 1998.

Current E-Fields measured at the Air Glow Building adjacent to PS1 exceed 4.4 Volts/Meter (added in quadrature). Most of this will be ameliorated by the re-location of commercial broadcasters under a grant from the Federal Government. The

Figure 17 Haleakala Seeing, as measured by Zirkind in 1965 with Baker-Nunn Camera. these are the most optimistic values, but were measured at a focal plane rather than by differential image motion.

Figure 18 Haleakala Seeing, R_0 versus time (Hawaii Standard Time) measured with the ATST DIMM on ATST Tower (about the height and isolation of PS1). This suggests there is 11 hours per night with median seeing less than or equal to 0.78 arcseconds, or 3 OTA pixels. (Night sky brightness is a separate issue, see the Section on twilight and length of night.) These are the most optimistic DIMM measurements made on Haleakala, see the Seeing Table for comparison.

TV broadcasters are being re-located to the distant Ulukalapua site, where terrain shielding should effectively eliminate them as a significant contributor to the Haleakala Observatory RFI. Note that the KOGG location and antenna design were intended to shield Haleakala Observatories, and the measured power at PS1 from this transmitter peaks slightly above -70 dBm, or $10^{-7}mW$.

Nonetheless, not all the Radio Frequency transmitters will be relocated and the items listed in red in Table 7 are expected to remain and are of concern. See Appendix D for RFI units and conversions.

3.3.4.1 NOAA - Commerce Department

The NOAA Services are of note because although they were present and operational, at the time of the above RFI Studies, they were not called out specifically, probably due their closeness in frequency. It is possible that the NOAA transmitters contribute significantly to the field strength attributed to the Navy, Justice Department, and Commerce Dept transmitters. However, the NOAA Services are moving from the AGR building and Lees site adjacent to the PS1 building to the Coast Guard (CG) tower. The CG tower is still within the Haleakala Observatory Site, but is several hundred meters further away. As we are in the "near-field" of these transmitters, small distances make a substantial difference. The 0.51 V/meter (in red, added in quadrature) expected to be left after currently planned re-location efforts may be an upper limit. On the other hand, the impact of the FAA transmitters is unknown; they were functional at the time of studies but were not singled out in the studies, perhaps due to their proximity in frequency to Channel 7 TV.

3.3.4.2 Other Local, Federal, and unknown transmitters

The Kona EMS and Hospital repeaters will remain, sporadic impact unknown. The impact of the other transmitters belonging to Federal agencies, Departments, and branches of the US military is unknown, some are likely to be time dependent. There appears to be a substantial amount of integrated power in the USAF low frequency side band transmitter.

The FAA VHF transmitters are repeaters, and thus time dependent. Only a long term synoptic study will determine the impact of these sources.

The FAA Digital Relays (FXC) at high frequency (1712-1483 MHz) have not been studied and their impact is unknown. Their purpose is to link lower density communications facilities to its nationwide microwave communications system. They are designed to be highly directional, but PS1 is not very far from direction of the relay facing east. and highly directional.

There remain unknown sources of Radio Frequency Interference at Haleakala Observatories that are seen in the radio spectrum analyzer, but whose origin has not been identified. In the US, the band from 225 to 400 MHz is for exclusive use of the US government for fixed and satellite transmitters. There are certainly a number of detected transmissions at Haleakala Observatories in this band.

3.3.4.3 Effects of Everyday RF Transmission on CCD systems

Cell phones can project $48,000 \mu W/m^2$, far in excess of the IAU limit. We have documented the negative impact of cell phone transmissions on CCD systems in the lab. Two-way Radios, or Family Radio Service type walkie-talkies are limited to 0.5 Watts and 450-470 MHz transmissions, however they can still cause an incorrect temperature to be sensed from the silicon diodes in the controller, which in turn cause the controller to overcorrect on the order of 5 degrees Kelvin, an unacceptable change in CCD temperature.

Table 7. Commercial and Institutional Sources of Radio Frequency Interference for PS1

Owner	Service	Call Sign	Freq. MHz	Tx Power kW	AGR ^a E Field V/m	ZLR ^b E Field V/m	MEES ^c E Field V/m	OGL ^d E Field V/m	Location and Status
USAF Side-band	SB, ALE Digital	MARS	20-39	?	?	?	?	?	Not Moving ^e
Ch 3 TV Video	NTSC Analog	KGMV	60-66	72.4	1.43	1.09	0.25	0.100	Moving to TS ^f Ulupalakua
Ch 3	Audio	KGMB	65.5	14.1	0.36	0.21	0.88	0.030	Moving to TS Ulupalakua
HI Public Radio	NPR FM Radio	KKUA	90.7	7	0.59	0.21	0.21	0.058	Moving to TS Ulupalakua
FAA VHF	Analog Repeat	Hono Cntr.	119.3	?	?				Not Moving
FAA VHF	Analog Repeat	Hono Cntr.	124.1	?	?				Not Moving
FAA VHF	Analog Repeat	Hono Cntr.	126.0	?	?				Not Moving
FAA VHF	Analog Repeat	Hono Cntr.	127.6	?	?				Not Moving
FAA VHF	Analog Repeat	ATIS-Maui	128.6	?	?				Not Moving
US Navy	MIL		131.5	?	0.42	?	?	?	T-pole/whip ^g HO ^h
US Gov	Unidentifi ed		138-144	?	?	?	?	?	Not Moving
Justice Dept.	FBI(?)		162.1	?	0.15	0.049	0.054	0.012	T-pole/whip HO
Commerce Dept.	NOAA NWS	KBA99	162.55/165.7	?	? ⁱ	?	?	?	Moving to GC ^j Tower HO
Commerce Dept.	NOAA NWR	WWG75	162.4	1	? ⁱ	?	?	?	Moving to GC Tower HO
Treasury Dept	SS (?)		165.2	?	0.25	0.100	0.035	0.003	T-pole/whip HO
Ch 7 TV Video	NTSC analog	KAII	174-180	50	3.16	0.220	0.199	0.060	Moving to TS Ulupalakua
Ch 7	Audio	KAII	179.6	29.5	1.27	0.067	0.054	0.004	Moving to TS Ulupalakua
Ch 10 TV Video	NTSC analog	KMEB	192-198	31.6	2.05	0.200	0.180	0.063	Moving to TS Ulupalakua
Ch 10	Audio	KMEB	197.6	?	0.61	0.058	0.046	0.020	Moving to TS Ulupalakua
Ch 12 TV Video	NTSC analog	KMAU	204-210	37.2	0.83	0.039	0.056	0.011	Moving to TS Ulupalakua
Ch 12	Audio	KMAU	209.3	?	0.16	0.013	0.010	0.007	Moving to TS Ulupalakua
Navy	Ship Com		216-220	?	?				Not Moving
Ham	HAM		445	?	?		0.001		Moving to Unknown
US Fed.Gov.	Fed Agencies		420-450	?	?				Not Moving
Coast Guard/Navy	Ship Sur.?		455	?	?				Not Moving
CH 16	TV NTSC analog	KOGG	476-482	759	?				TS, DIR ^k (?)
CH 16	Digital TV	KOGG	482-488	?	?				TS, DIR CP ^l
Kona EMS Repeater	LTR Trunked	EMS	453.35	1	?				Not Moving
Kona Hospital	Carrier	Medic	462.2	?	?				Not Moving
CH 46 Translator	PURI FAM	NEW	662-668	25	NA				License Applied For
FAA 010695	Trans. Digital	FXC	1712	10	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 981464	Trans. Digital	FXC	1725	10	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 960861	Receiver Digital	FXC	1720	NA	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 980711	Receiver Digital	FXC	1745	NA	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 831157	Receiver Digital	FXC	1757.5	NA	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 010696	Receiver Digital	FXC	1766	NA	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 931362	Receiver Digital	FXC	1792.5	NA	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 980132	Receiver Digital	FXC	1785	NA	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 001258	Trans. Digital	FXC	1805	10	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 931451	Trans. Digital	FXC	1809	10	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 960862	Trans. Digital	FXC	1842	10	?				FAA MWR HO DIR
FAA 931443	Trans. Digital	FXC	1843	10	?				FAA MWR HO DIR

^aAGR: Air Glow Building, closest to PS1 Site;

^bZLR: Zodiacal Light Building;

^cMEES: Mees Solar Observatory, Partially Terrain Shielded from Lees Enterprises Antenna Farm;

^dOGL: Outside Ground Level, west of Mees;

^eItems in red of concern for PS1 Science Mission;

^fTS: Terrain Sheilded. Note items in black are major issues during commissioning of PS1, but not expected to be of concern for the PS1 Science Mission;

^gT-pole/whip: Mounted on Telephone poles at West end of HO, fiberglass whip antennas;

^hHO: Haleakala Observatory;

ⁱE-Field from NOAA transmitters could have been included in the measurements of the Justice and Treasury Department transmitters at adjacent frequencies;

^jCG: Coast Guard, NOAA, the NOAA NWS and NWR transmitters currently bracket PS1 with one at the Lees Site and one on the AGR

^kDirectional Antenna Pattern;

^lConstruction Permit obtained;

Figure 19 Radio Spectrum as observed outside on the roof of the PS1 Support Building. The x-axis is linear in units of MHz, from 0 to 500 MHz, with vertical lines every 50 MHz. The y-axis is in decibels, it is equivalent to a logarithmic scale covering 8 decades, ranging from $10^{-8}mW$ to $1mW$. In the US, the band from 225 to 400 MHz is for exclusive use of the US government for fixed and satellite transmitters. There are certainly a number of detected transmissions in this band. See Appendix D. The observed radio spectrum is currently being monitored and archived 24 hours a day.

WiFi Hubs, microwave ovens, etc., although very useful to have in the observatory during commissioning, need to be tested to examine their impact on observations. Most of these sources of RF Transmission will be mitigated by operating remotely during normal survey operations, but are an issue during commissioning.

3.3.4.4 GPC1 Susceptibility

The GPC1 Camera and its controllers constitute such a complicated electrical system that it is not possible to estimate the susceptibility of the system to a given radio signal. For example, initial measurements show the camera is sensitive to the NTSC line rate (15.7 KHz) from the current television broadcasters. Furthermore, an intermittent transmitter at 138.9 is tentatively correlated with noise in the detector.

These sensitivities could not have been predicted. Thus although 89 percent of the EM field will go away with the planned re-location, we will only be able to determine empirically the impact of the remaining RFI on the PS1 System.

3.3.4.5 Ongoing RFI Studies and Mitigation

The Analyser antenna has now been transferred to the PS1 dome, and the RF spectrum at the site is being archived 24 hours a day.

By correlating time dependent RFI and time dependent sources of noise in the TC3 and GPC1 cameras, before and after antenna relocation, it may be possible to identify and implement various kinds of shielding and other mitigation strategies to reduce Camera susceptibility to RFI.

Figure 20 Right: the 3 degree field of view of PS1 with an inscribed hexagon of 5.84 square degrees. Left: Outside view of the celestial sky tessellated into 6252 fields. Of these fields, 5464 have boresight centers ≥ -30 degrees Declination.

3.4 Geometrical Constraints

3.4.1 GPC1 Focal Plane

The Camera has a circular field of view of 3 degrees diameter. This field is sampled by 60 OTA chips, each with 64 cells of 600 x 600 pixels. Along the outside edges of the detector, the detector does not quite reach the edge of the field of view. There are also 8 OTA chips in the corners where that the detector extends well beyond the circular field of view. These regions will be used for wavefront sensing using calcite blocks and optics to create above and below focus images of stars in these regions.

The net effect however is that an inscribed hexagon within the circular field of view is rotated with respect to the pixel direction. See Figure 20.

3.4.2 Observing Tessellation

For large regions of the sky, the observing footprint will be laid down in an approximately hexagonal spacing due to the circular field of view. This implies 20 percent area overlap from adjacent hexagonal spacings as large regions of the sky are mapped. The baseline PS1 Observing Tessellation comes from a geodesic subdivision of a truncated icosahedron (soccer ball). See Figure 20. The tessellation devised by Chambers is extremely efficient at mapping the sky with PS1 focal plane, the extra area is no more than 2 percent than if it were tiling a flat surface instead of a sphere.

3.5 Astronomical Constraints

3.5.1 Twilight

The length of the time during a given clear night available for observing depends on the time of year, and the Filter bandpass. Twilight, the time at which the night sky brightness becomes as dark as it going to become due to scattered

Table 8. Twilight per PS1 Filter

Filter	Degrees Sun is below horizon	Twilight
<i>g</i> band	18°	Astronomical Twilight
<i>r</i> band	18°	Astronomical Twilight
<i>i</i> band	12°	Civil Twilight
<i>z</i> band	8°	Near IR Twilight
<i>y</i> band	8°	Near IR Twilight

Table 9. Allowable Lunar Illumination per PS1 Filter

Filter	Lunar illumination	Moon Distance Degrees
<i>g</i> band	< 5%	90
<i>r</i> band	< 5% (TBR)	90
<i>i</i> band	≤ 100%	30
<i>z</i> band	≤ 100%	30
<i>y</i> band	≤ 100%	30

sunlight, is dependent on the bandpass and is determined observationally on a photometric night by noting in evening twilight when the sky brightness stops decreasing, and in the morning twilight (dawn) when the sky brightness begins to increase. For the standard bands these are well known; not as obvious is how much longer the night time is in *z* and *y* band. See Table 9. The length of the night over the year is plotted below in the section on the PS1 Observing Scheduler.

3.5.2 Lunar illumination

Lunar illumination has little effect on the sky background seen in the *i*, *z*, and *y* filters, as long as the moon is far enough away from the field being imaged. However *g* and *r* band are strongly affected by scattered moon light, and except for the MD fields, observations in *g* and *r* should be in dark time. See Table 9.

4 Estimated PS1 Sensitivities

The parameters required to estimate the sensitivity of PS1 in each band-pass are given in 11 and 21. Details of the PS1 filter specifications are given in PSDC-330-002.

The parameters required to estimated the sensitivity of PS1 in each band-pass given in Table 10 The magnitude that produces 1 electron/sec/pixels is computed assuming 75 micron thick chips, aluminum coatings on the mirrors, an effective loss of 0.35 area from secondary mirror blockage and diffraction from baffles and secondary mirror support structure from a 1.8 meter diameter collecting area, and nominal atmospheric absorption and scattering. The average sky brightness μ in magnitudes per square arcsec at Haleakala assumes the Wainscoat light pollution factor in *g* and *r* band. A mean air mass of 1.4 is assumed.

The effective sensitivity is then characterized by the magnitude m_1 above the atmosphere that produces $1e^-/\text{sec/pixel}$

Figure 21 PS1 Throughput.

Table 10. PS1 Sensitivity Parameters

Filter	Bandpass (nm)	m_1 AB mag	μ AB mag/asec ²
<i>g</i>	405–550	24.90	21.90
<i>r</i>	552–689	25.15	20.86
<i>i</i>	691–815	25.00	20.15
<i>z</i>	815–915	24.63	19.26
<i>y</i>	967–1024	23.03	17.98

at the detector. This depends on the total throughput of the atmosphere, the reflectivity of the telescope mirrors, the transmission of the corrector optics and filters, and the quantum efficiency of the camera detector - all of which are wavelength dependent.

The signal from a given source of total apparent magnitude m , in exposure time t seconds, and assuming PSF fitting photometry, is:

$$S = t \times \frac{1}{2} \times 10^{-0.4(m-m_1)}.$$

The noise N comes from a combination of sources of variance: the Poisson noise of the source counts, $\sigma_P^2 = 0.5 \times 10^{-0.4(m-m_1)}t$; the variance from the sky background, $\sigma_S^2 = \frac{\pi}{4}\omega^2 \times 10^{-0.4(\mu-m_1)}t$, where ω is the FWHM of the PSF in arcseconds, and μ is sky brightness in magnitudes per square arcsecond; the variance from the read-noise of the detector $\sigma_{RN}^2 = \frac{\pi}{4}\omega^2 \times A \times N_{read}^2$ where $A = 14.79$ pixels/arcsec² for 0.26 arcsecond pixels, and N_{read} is the read noise of the detector; the variance from any Radio Frequency Interference (i.e. an increase in effective read-noise that is seen at the summit of Haleakala, but not in the laboratory¹) $\sigma_{RFI}^2 = \frac{\pi}{4}\omega^2 \times A \times N_{RFI}^2$; the variance due to dark current D counts/sec $\sigma_D^2 = \frac{\pi}{4}\omega^2 \times A \times Dt$; and the variance due to the dilution of the signal over a larger area due to motion of an NEO during an exposure, where these trailing losses are small, is $\sigma_T^2 = \frac{1}{6}(tR_{NEO}/\omega)^2(\sigma_S^2 + \sigma_{RN}^2 + \sigma_{RFI}^2 + \sigma_D^2)$ where the average trailing rate for NEO's is taken to be $R_{NEO} \approx 0.02$ arcsec/second, or half a degree per day. The signal-to-noise ratio for a given observation is then:

$$S/N = S/\sqrt{\sigma_P^2 + \sigma_S^2 + \sigma_{RN}^2 + \sigma_{RFI}^2 + \sigma_T^2 + \sigma_D^2}$$

where each individual variance is given in the text above.

Note, for the 3π survey, the read noise is a non-negligible contribution to the noise to a single exposure time. Thus one can not compute the total 3 year sensitivity from the total 3 year exposure time using the above equation. One must calculate the variance for a single exposure, and then combine these single exposure variances appropriately for the total combined measurement or image stack.

5 PS1 Surveys

The time distribution in Table 1 comes from the agreement laid out in the PS1 Science Consortium Memorandum of Agreement, and the supporting documents. Progress of the surveys will be monitored by the Survey Strategy Working Group (SSWG), and reported regularly to the PS1SC Board, with recommendations. If the observing falls systematically behind the schedule, the default strategy for addressing the problem was set forth in the PS1 Mission Concept Statement. The SSWG will determine what if any changes need to be made in the survey strategy.

5.1 The 3π Steradian Survey

To meet the PS1 Science Goals, including the all sky precision photometric and astrometric survey required for high fidelity image registration and subtraction, we have found from studies with the PS1 Scheduler, described below, and modified from the LSST simulator, that a single all sky 3π steradian survey is much more efficient than two separate surveys, e.g. a astrometric and photometric survey that requires the available photometric time, and a separate Opposition Survey for NEOs. By combining the time for these two surveys into a single all sky survey the telescope can be scheduled significantly more efficiently than for two distinct surveys. This approach guarantees that the NEOO search program gets all the photometric time on Haleakala. It also extends the NEOO search program to the celestial pole, as opposed to +40 ecliptic latitude, and more than doubles the total time that can be spent observing at the appropriate NEO cadence. By

matching the depth of each pass-band, and by using the appropriate pass-band for a given lunar phase, the efficiency is further increased, as bright time would severely limit the sensitivity of a wide bandpass w filter. With this strategy, 60 percent of PS1 observing time can be spent on an opposition survey optimized with the NEO cadence.

For the 3π Survey, the entire sky available from Hawaii will be surveyed in 5 bandpasses from a declination of -30 to the North Celestial Pole. This is $3/4$ of the entire celestial sphere, or 3π Steradians. This survey is expected to use approximately 56 percent of the total observing time, and address aspects of all of the the primary science goals above. More than half of this time is expected to be photometric. It remains to be seen how well we can combine data from nights with sparsely distributed clouds ("photometric in patches") and nights with thin cirrus, with the truly photometric nights, but simulations show the best approach is to maintain a constant survey strategy, rather than separate a photometric survey with cadence requirements from a non-photometric survey with cadence requirements.

The entire sky can be surveyed with the exposure times listed in 11 with 4 visits per year in each of three bands g, r, i, z, y . Each night that a given field is observed, it is visited twice, with the pair of images separated by a Transient Time Interval, (TTI) of approximately 30-60 minutes to distinguish moving solar system objects from stationary transient objects. Although not planned at this time, we have examined the option of using back-to-back exposures to improve the "instantaneous" sensitivity to moving objects, and this may be a strategy that should be revisited after experience with the PS1 system and further algorithm and code development.

By choosing sky regions, bandpasses, and cadences carefully, and accounting for the historical weather pattern, we hope to cover the entire sky north of -30 degrees declination 4 times in each band pass g, r, i, z, y every year.

Figure 22 shows the schematic outline of the strategy devised for the 3π survey, and Figure 23 details the filter selection and area coverage within the lunar cycle. These are schematic, the scheduling of the seasonal length of the night, lunar illumination, and lunar rise and set times, the re-synchronization of the observing cycle to adjust for the synodic lunar period versus the sidereal cycle are addressed in detail by the simulated Design Reference Mission (DRM) discussed below.

The basic observing strategy is to obtain 2 visits (exposures) of a given field in a single night per lunation in each of five colors. Every field is then observed over two lunations, giving 4 visits (exposures) per color per year. The exposure times of the g, r, i bands are balanced to provide approximately uniform depth for the mean color of asteroids, so that there are a minimum of 3 pairs of observations per lunation, and two lunations per year, or six epochs for orbit determination per year in the 3π survey.

The y band observations are taken in the areas adjacent to the opposition survey for scheduling reasons, and will give additional linkages for bright objects.

The z band is taken in twilight for optimizing the parallax detections. The end of twilight in z band, and the onset of constant sky brightness (no moon) starts approximately one half hour after sunset and ends approximately one half hour before sunrise. This allows us to make effective use of time before the end of standard astronomical twilight. The seeing at twilight is typically worse than a few hours after twilight, so the evening z band limiting magnitude may suffer from this. See Figure 18.

More than half of the clear time is expected to be photometric. It remains to be seen how well we can combine data from nights with sparsely distributed clouds ("photometric in patches") and nights with thin cirrus. The stacking of images, and the number of stacked images that will be produced and saved are a Science Consortium and storage issue. It may be desirable to produce more than one static sky image, where the the combined stacked images are combined by different algorithms to optimize one or more of the following: image quality (seeing), photometric accuracy, image differencing, sensitivity to point sources, sensitivity to extended surface brightness, preservation of morphology, preservation of astrometric accuracy.

For Solar System studies, it is important to note that the the mean color of asteroids is $(g-r) = 0.44$, and $(r-i)=0.14$, or

Table 11. Estimated Sensitivities for the 3π Survey. The tabulated numbers use the above equations and assume 75 micron chips, aluminum coating, effective loss of 0.35 area from secondary mirror blockage and diffraction from baffles and secondary mirror support structure. The average sky brightness μ at Haleakala assumes the Wainscoat light pollution factor in g and r band, and an average air mass of 1.4 is assumed. The FWHM is taken to be 0.78 arcsec, or three pixels assuming OTA improvement. A read noise of 5 electrons rms is assumed, and an optimistic zero contribution from RFI.

Filter	Bandpass (nm)	m_1 AB mag	μ AB mag/asec ²	exposure time/visit sec	5σ trailed NEO/visit	5σ pt. source per visit	visits in one night	visits per year	visits per 3 yrs	5σ pt. source in 3 yrs
g	405–550	24.90	21.90	60	23.08	23.24	2	4	12	24.66
r	552–689	25.15	20.86	38	22.63	22.71	2	4	12	24.11
i	691–815	25.00	20.15	60	22.47	22.63	2	4	12	23.96
z	815–915	24.63	19.26	30	21.53	21.59	2	4	12	22.98
y	967-1024	23.03	17.98	30	20.08	20.13	2	4	12	21.52

Table 12. Pessimistic Saturation Limits for 3π Survey Many brighter stars will be obtained in guide-star video mode. The pre-ucam ISP zeropoints are around 19, so with with the re-built ISP and ucam2, we expect the PS1 stellar catalog to have a dynamic range from 6th magnitude to the limiting magnitude of the 3π Survey.

Filter	Exp time sec	Saturation magnitude limit
g	60	18.2
r	38	17.9
i	30	17.5
z	30	17.3
y	30	15.5

solar color. The depths given for trailed NEO’s (0.5 degree per day) show that for an asteroid of solar color, the 5 sigma detection limit in each band, given its exposure time and the trailing loss associated with that exposure time, is the same in each band. To convert to units familiar to the NEO and asteroid community, Johnson V band is, for solar colors, approximately $V = r + 0.4$, thus the trailed NEO single exposure sensitivity is equivalent to $V = 23$ in $g, r,$ and i bands.

For objects moving significantly slower than 0.5 degrees per day, the point source sensitivity should be used. For NEOs with trailing losses, and putting in the requirement that tracklets that require two detections, this means the PS1 sensitivity, for the given exposure times and assumptions quoted in 11, are for the "discovery of tracklets" is equivalent to a 5 sigma limiting magnitude of $V=22.8$.

For galactic and extragalactic studies the 3 year stacked point source sensitivity is slightly optimistic because it assumes all the time is photometric when there will be some data in the total stacked image from less than photometric conditions, and thus should be considered uncertain by a few tenths of a magnitude.

5.1.1 Calibration fields for 3π Survey

Approximately every hour the 3π survey will visit one of 20 calibration fields. Filter changes as required will occur on calibration fields, For example after an hour in I band, the telescope will slew to the nearest calibration field, take a 30 second I band exposure, if necessary for the next survey field it will change filters on the calibration field, take an image

Table 13. Estimated PS1 Sensitivities for the Medium Deep Survey. The tabulated numbers use the same assumptions as those listed for the 3pi Survey.

Filter	Bandpass (nm)	m_1 AB mag	μ AB mag/asec ²	exp time sec	5σ point source in 4 nts	5σ point source in 1 yr	5σ point source in 3 yrs
<i>g</i>	405–550	24.90	21.90	3 × 240	24.80	26.72	27.32
<i>r</i>	552–689	25.15	20.85	3 × 240	24.44	26.36	26.96
<i>i</i>	691–815	25.00	20.15	6 × 240	24.38	26.31	26.91
<i>z</i>	815–915	24.63	19.26	6 × 240	23.77	25.69	26.29
<i>y</i>	967–1024	23.03	17.98	6 × 240	22.32	24.24	24.84

in the new filter, and then proceed. The calibration fields will thus compose a modestly deep set of images obtained in all colors on a regular basis.

Some of the calibration fields have to be standard photometric fields to obtain consistency with other calibrations. But any field can in principle serve as a calibration fields, and all of the Medium Deep Survey (described below) fields will also serve as calibration fields. These fields can be used for a wide range of auxiliary science projects, the primarily requirement is that the overall distribution is approximately uniform across the sky, and that some are standard photometric fields. Observations of calibration fields are expected to use 2 percent of the photometric telescope time.

Fields from the Medium Deep Survey, the Deep M31 Survey, and the Stellar Transit Survey will also be used in the total set of calibration fields. The complete set of calibration fields are listed in Appendix C.

5.2 Medium Deep Survey

The Medium Deep Survey consists of 10 GPC1 footprints spaced approximately uniformly around the sky optimized for studies of SN1a. The fields are listed in Appendix A. Seven of these fields are expected to be observable on a given night. Each of the seven fields will be observed every usable night. The observing cadence will be to cycle through five colors in a four days. For example on day 1 of the four day cycle, the *g* and *r* bands will be observed. Then on days 2, 3, and 4 the field will be observed in *i*, *z*, and *y*. The cycle is then repeated. Weather losses are simply accepted as lost data. Assuming 0.65 percent of nights in a year are clear, then each year a given field is observed, on average, 138.4 nights.

The depth of this survey is designed to measure the epoch of re-acceleration and placing limits or detecting cosmological quintessence. The nightly depth is chosen to detect SN1a at $z \approx 0.5$. The stacked images constitute an 84 square degree survey capable of detecting L^* evolved galaxies at redshift $z \sim 1.8$.

The expected sensitivities are given in Table 13.

5.3 Solar System Sweet Spot Survey

Each lunation approximately 500 square degrees in each of two "sweet spots" will be observed twice a night, separated by approximately a one half hour Transient Time Interval. This region is currently scheduled to be re-observed three times a lunation, preferably spaced by about 4 days. Without an ADC, this must be done in a normal filter. The greatest sensitivity for solar colors in the least amount of time is the *i* band. This will have the same equivalent $V = 22.8$ for "discovery tracklets", not point source detection. However, since the observations will be at high airmass, one expects greater losses from extinction and seeing.

5.4 Stellar Transit Survey

The goal of the Stellar Transit Survey (STS), is to find ≈ 100 Hot Jupiters by detecting the transit of such an object in the light curves of millions of stars visible in the proposed survey fields.

The STS fields and Campaigns are listed in Appendix B. Campaign #1 is a field in the galactic buldge. For this Campaign there will be three adjacent GPC1 footprints. Each field will be observed with a 2 minutes exposure, including read and slew time, repeating every 6 minutes. Each campaign is to be scheduled for 120 hours per year, and it is expected that this time will be reduced by the same fraction as that due to weather and average observing efficiency factors as the rest of the PS1 Mission.

The observations will be scheduled in 3 hours contiguous blocks per transit night unless it can be conclusively demonstrated that shorter contiguous blocks produce superior relative photometric data.

The STS field will be used as a standard PS1 calibration field as well.

5.5 Deep Survey of M31

The Andromeda Galaxy, M31, is extremely well suited to Deep Survey with the PS1 System. The field will be used as a standard calibration field as well.

5.5.1 Microlensing in M31

Self-lensing provides a unique way to measure the stellar mass function in the bulge of M31 down to the faintest stars and brown dwarfs, where direct resolved photometry is not possible. The proposed dedicated survey to micro-lensing in M31 is expected to produce at least 300 self lensing events per year, with 50 MACHO events if the dark halo is 10 percent MACHOs.

The strategy for the Microlensing experiment is to observe M31 every night that it is available, and the optimal strategy is to obtain 2 visits per night of observation, separated by up to 5 hours, with approximately 360 seconds total integration per visit in r band for a minimum of 10 consecutive weeks each year. This is 720 seconds every night. Additional colors shall be included for a total time up to 720 seconds every night for 5 months per year.

5.6 Pan-STARRS Project Principal Investigator Discretionary Time

Of the total expected time, 6% is reserved for discretionary time as determined by the Pan-STARRS Principal Investigator.

6 Survey Strategy

The cadences for the PS1 surveys are in Table 14. The basic survey strategy is to begin the night with a parallax field in z band (bright time), followed by a calibration field. After twilight the sweet spot survey is done in r band during grey-dark time, When it is bright time the y band observations of the 3 pi survey can begin. followed by a calibration field and a Medium Deep, M31, or STS field. Then, depending on lunar phase the 3pi Survey is carried out with revisits on a TTI time scale. Interleaved are Calibration fields, Medium Deep Fields, M31 observations, and the STS fields. In the morning the eastern sweet spot observations are carried out, followed by the z band parallax observations.

Table 14. The PS1 Survey Cadences for perfect weather

PS1 Surveys	Filters total exposure visit	Visits per night per fi eld	Separation of visits in one night	Separation of nights per fi eld	Visits per lunation per fi eld	Visits per year per fi eld	Visits per 3 year per fi eld
3 π Steradian Survey	g, r, i, z, y						
opposition region	60 $g, 38r, 30i$	2	TTI	4,5 days	2 x 3 bands	4 x 3 bands	36 x 3 bands
adjacent to opposition region	30 y	2	TTI	4,5 days	2 x 1 band	4 x 1 band	12 x 1 bands
180 degree parallax fi elds	30 z	2	TTI	4,5 days	2 x 1 band	4 x 1 band	12 x 1 bands
Calibration Fields	30 $g, 30r, 30i, 30z, 30y$	10/25	1 - 2 TTI	varies	varies	180 per band	540 per band
Medium Deep Survey	720 g, r, i, z, y	5-7/10	0	1	30	$\sim 6 \times 30$	9 x 30
Solar System Sweet Spot Survey	30 r	2	TTI	4,5 days	2 x 1 band	4 x 1 band	12 x 1 band
Stellar Transit Survey	30x60 i	30	4 min	4, 5 days	$\sim 5 \times 30$	~ 150	
Deep Survey of M31	g, r, i, z, y	2	0 to 5 hours	1	30 to 60	$\sim 45 \times 5$	~ 675

Table 15. The PS1 Rotator and Raster Strategy for PS1 Surveys

PS1 Surveys	Filters	Raster/pointing	Field selection	Caveats and TBRs
3 π Steradian Survey	g, r, i, z, y			
TTI opposition region	g, ri, i, y	exact same pointing/night	Seasonal variation	with 90, 180, 270 as per RRR
lunation opposition region	g, ri, i, y	alternating tessellation/month	Seasonal variation	
TTI parallax region	z	exact same pointing/night		with 90, 180, 270 as per RRR
parallax region	z	alternating tessellation from E to W	No Seasonal variation	
year to year	g, r, i, z, y	new pair of tesslations per year		
Calibration Fields	$g, r, i, z, y,$	same pointing/campaign	Add 6 rotating half fi eld offsets	short exposure mode (TBR)
Medium Deep Survey	g, r, i, z, y	same pointing for 4 nights	rotate per 4 nights per year	
Solar System Sweet Spot Survey				
TTI	r	exact same point/night	No Seasonal variation	with 90, 180, 270 as per RRR
lunation	r	alternating tessellation/month	No Seasonal variation	
Stellar Transit Survey	i	exact same pointing/campaign		with 90, 180, 270 as per RRR
Deep Survey M31				
Microlensing	r	exact same point/campaign		(TBR)
Deep multiband survey	g, i, z, y		rotate per 4 nights per year	(TBR)

The execution of the 3π survey is illustrated Figure 22 and Figure 23.

7 Implications of the Survey Strategy for exploration of the time domain

Because the high quality image area is circular and covered by the camera, 20 percent of the sky will be covered with three images, (12 for i band) due to the overlapping regions of adjacent footprints. This provides a substantial amount of sky coverage with a 30 second cadence. This is important for transient detections as well as providing greater depth. By careful choice of subsequent field centers from visit to visit, we can effectively cover the sky with 7 observations at each point with 6 visits.

8 The PS1 Observing Scheduler

The PS1 Surveys constitute a proposal for use of the PS1 System. The execution of those surveys is measured against a Design Reference Mission, which is intended to be a realistic simulation, complete with historical weather stream, to examine how well we can actually expect to carry out the PS1 Science Mission to some reasonable level of fidelity. Below we describe the PS1 Scheduler, and a specific initial simulation of the PS1 Design Reference Mission, called DRM1-v3. The Scheduler is not yet capable of a full simulation of all aspects of the PS1 Surveys, but the results are illustrative. A high fidelity simulation is expected in the next release of the Design Reference Mission. At that time not only is the scheduler expected to have the full fidelity of the PS1 Surveys, but from commissioning we will know things that are currently only approximations: e.g. the read noise at the summit in the RFI environment of Halaekala Observatories, the seeing at the PS1 site and the image quality of the PS1 system, and the photometric and astrometric performance.

8.1 PS1 Scheduler Overview

The PS1 Observing Scheduler is a derivative of the LSST cadence simulator, a research tool created by LSST to evaluate performance of various proposed scheduling strategies. LSST has graciously provided this code to Pan-STARRS. Pan-STARRS has contributed to ongoing development of the common cadence simulator source code, and has recently substantially modified the original simulator code to address DRM requirements within Pan-STARRS.

Fundamentally the scheduler is implemented using SimPy, a Python-language discrete event simulator package. Configuration files describe telescope hardware parameters, site parameters, and surveying rules. Observing commands generated by the scheduler are stored in a MySQL database for later analysis or import into OTIS's current telescope control package. External synthetic weather streams can be injected into the scheduler to simulate real losses due to clouds, poor seeing or high humidity. The scheduler selects its boresight locations from a fixed tessellation stored in its database.

The scheduler operates by starting its internal clock at the beginning of a simulation, then repeatedly evaluating the "best field" to visit given its surveying rules, current physical limits, and current state (fields already acquired). At any given instant in simulator time, some number of tessellation fields (possibly zero) are eligible for observation. Each eligible field is assigned a score, called a *ranking*, computed based on a number of considerations, such as slew or rotation time to reach a field or the field's contribution to some larger scheduling goal. All eligible fields are given a ranking, and the scheduler chooses the highest ranking field.

Figure 22 PS1 Survey Strategy. The colored boxes represent sections of the sky in a "mercator-like" rectangular projection - it shows the sky from $-30 \leq \delta \leq 90$, and each colored box represents approximately 2 hours in Right Ascension or 30 degrees at the equator in this projection. Going down the the staircase is in the time direction, with each step a step approximately once per lunation, and shifting constantly to the East as the year progresses. After one year, the survey is back where it started from on the sky. The center of each observed region is approximately at Solar opposition at new moon. This is schematic. In the detailed schedule the size of each region must be longer in the winter and shorter in the summer by more than 10 percent to account for the change in the length of the night. Further adjustments to the scheduling are required to match the synodic lunar period with the annual sidereal period.

For the 3pi Survey, one year is divided into 12 regions to be observed in approximately 29.3 days each. The size of the regions will not be a constant 2 hours in RA because of the seasonal length of the night. The observing pattern shown for each lunation is centered at solar opposition at new moon and is represented at left as a Mercator projection from $-30 < \text{dec} < 90$. On average the pattern shifts to the East by two hours in RA each month. The details of syncing the lunar synodic period with the sidereal sky are presented in the DRM.

Each box shows the filter and the number of exposures obtained per night (always 2, separated by a TTI). The length of the exposures in each band varies, and is given in the table in the text.

The end result is the coverage shown in the top summary panel, and on the graphic demonstrating the year long graphic. The ability to achieve this survey has included the average weather pattern and expected slew times and read times. Every part of the sky is observed 20 times per year, 4 in each of 5 filters. The variations of this schematic to account for the seasonal length in RA of the boxes and the synchronization of lunar synodic and sidereal are given in the PS1 DRM

Figure 23 Detailed survey strategy within a lunation, showing the approximate filter balance and area coverage.

8.2 Scheduler Concepts

8.3 Terminology

The following terms are essential to understanding the scheduler.

- Tessellation : a collection of spherical positions from which telescope pointings will be selected
- Field : a boresight position, obtained from one of the tessellation points or some other collection of boresite positions (e.g., Calibration, Medium-Deep)
- Observing Cycle : a time duration one lunation in length, starting on a full moon. Many scheduler operations respect Observing Cycle boundaries.
- Transient Time Interval (TTI) : a nominal time separation between two fields, useful for locating and characterizing moving objects.

8.4 Configuration Files

The scheduler's behavior is controlled using various configuration files, which are text files containing key-value assignments in the form *param = value*. Configuration files may contain shell-style comments using the hash (#) character. The following sections describe the configuration files used by the scheduler.

8.5 Site Parameters

The site config file *siteConf* contains site-specific parameters, listed in Table 5.

8.6 Telescope Parameters

The telescope configuration file *instrumentConf* contains a description of the telescope hardware and dependency relationships between components, listed in Table 3. The Filter properties are given in Section 3.2.6.

8.7 Proposals

The main component in controlling the scheduler's behavior is a *proposal*. A proposal is a configuration file specifying rules governing which tessellation fields should be observed and when. There are about a dozen different proposal types, meaning that their code modules implement particular types of behaviors that can be customized using a configuration files for each proposal type. Some proposal types implemented by LSST include

- NearEarthProp, an ecliptic-plane proposal that observes using cadences optimized for asteroid discovery, possibly lunation-oriented
- WeakLensProp, an all-sky proposal that attempts to observe all tessellation fields a configured number of times
- SuperNovaProp, a proposal that observes fixed positions at regular intervals

- SuperNovaSubSeqProp, a supernova proposal that allows “subsequences,” or uninterrupted blocks of multiple exposures and filters

8.8 Pan-STARRS General Proposals

Early Pan-STARRS scheduler development attempted to use proposal types provided by LSST with small modifications to satisfy Pan-STARRS requirements. However after some development and analysis of simulation runs, we developed a project-specific “General” proposal type that could be used to implement most of the DRM mission.

The General proposal type allows specification of an anti-solar region of sky to be observed during a small window within a lunation and in a particular filter. The PS1 Mission Concept Statement divides the astrometric/photometric (3pi) survey into 28 regions that are observed using transient time interval (TTI)-separated observations within different time windows each lunation. Each of these regions is implemented using a General proposal. Additionally, sweetspot observing for the NEO survey follows similar rules and is implemented using two separate *ess* (evening sweetspot) and *mss* (morning sweetspot) General proposals.

8.9 Pan-STARRS Medium-Deep Proposals

The PS1 DRM Medium-Deep (MD) survey is implemented using a group of SuperNovaSubSeq proposals, modified to restrict observing to every N^{th} night, so that *gr* can be observed on one night, *i* the following night, *z* the next, and so on. Fields for the MD survey do not come from the fixed tessellation; instead they are pre-loaded using special IDs into the Field database.

8.10 Pan-STARRS Calibration Proposals

The PS1 Calibration proposal implements a simplistic proposal that observes the nearest calibration field in the current telescope filter at regular intervals.

8.11 A Pan-STARRS “Program”

A concept introduced in the Pan-STARRS version of the scheduler for accounting and analysis reasons is the *Program*. Groups of proposals are aggregated logically into programs so that their overall behavior can be analyzed by reporting tools. The program that a proposal belongs to has no bearing on its behavior during the simulation.

8.12 Observation Scheduler

The observation scheduler is a code module that computes a sky model profile then asks each of the configured proposals in the current simulation to provide rankings for each of their eligible fields. The highest-ranking field among all the proposals is selected as the field to observe. Following “observation” of the field (writing the observe commands to the database), the simulation idles for the slew time and exposure time and repeats the process.

Figure 24 Graphical description of scheduler observation windowing.

8.13 Sequences and Subsequences

Some proposals, such as the General and NearEarth proposals, allow specification of cadences of observations. These proposals understand a notion that if a first observation of a pair is acquired, the second observation must happen within a certain window of time. The code object that implements this knowledge is called a *Sequence*. When a Sequence-aware proposal starts up, each of its eligible fields is given a Sequence object that maintains state of the sequence. For example, it knows how many observations have been acquired (and possibly) missed for the sequence. When the observation scheduler asks each proposal for its ranked fields, the fields that belong to a sequence with time-sensitivity are given higher priority, at expense of other fields that are not time-sensitive.

The time intervals specified in a sequence are approximate. In other words, the scheduler is not expected to schedule subsequent observations in a sequence at the exact interval specified. Instead, there is a windowing function that indicates when the observation may be observed. The windowing function allows an observation to grow in ranking from a start time *WindowStart* until a time at which it has maximum ranking *WindowMax*, then the ranking decays back to zero at *WindowEnd* time, after which the observation is abandoned. This windowing gives the scheduler some flexibility in timing of observations that are to be separated by some nominal time. Figure 24 shows graphically how windowing is implemented.

8.14 Pan-STARRS Implementation of the PS1 Scheduler

The prototype PS1 DRM implementation of the scheduler configures six different scheduling programs using 36 different proposal definitions. Twenty eight of these proposals implement the PS1 3pi survey, and five implement the Medium-Deep surveys, STS and M31 surveys. The remaining proposals implement the sweetspot and calibration surveys.

8.15 3pi Region Modulation

The Pan-STARRS General proposal type allows for specification of a region fixed relative to the anti-solar point at the midpoint of an observing cycle. Due to the difference in night length over the course of a year, it is suboptimal to keep

Figure 25 Haleakala night lengths over one year.

these regions the same size. The General proposal supports a ModulateOppRA flag that requests that the scheduler modify the configured size to conform to an optimal strategy in which the opposition region grows and shrinks over the year.

In order to support this strategy, the center of the modulated opposition position varies sinusoidally with the true opposition point; half the year it is behind and the other half it is ahead. The length of night over the year is of course also sinusoidal, and the optimal strategy is for the length of observing time to be cosinusoidal starting on December 20, and the offset from the true opposition point to be sinusoidal (90 degrees behind). Conceptually, we can see that on December 20, when there is maximum observing time, we are maximally expanding our observing area and thus maximally integrating our “reserve” of observing time until the spring equinox, when we start “using up” our reserve. When the autumnal equinox arrives we once again start building our reserve observation time.

The exact amount of expansion that can be afforded is empirical, based on the annual range of night lengths in Hawaii and relative proportion of 3pi survey time to the entire DRM survey. Figure 25 shows a graph of approximate night lengths on Haleakala obtained by analyzing a year’s worth of scheduler output.

Based on this figure we calculate the maximum expansion coefficient M to be 0.13, the relative deviation of longest (11.44 hours) to average (10.12 hours) night length. Using this coefficient and the total width W of 120 degrees of the 3pi region, we compute the region scaling factor S in RA and offset from opposition δ_{opp} as

$$S = 1 + M \cos [2\pi(d - d_0)/365]$$

$$\delta_{opp} = (W/2)M \cos [2\pi(d - d_0)/365]$$

where d is the MJD of a given night of the survey and d_0 is the MJD for (any) December 20.

Figure 26 3pi survey coverage for observing cycle 89 (01-3piR-2007 through 30-3piR-2007). Note that the central 3pi region is slightly off-center due to region modulation described in Section 8.15.

9 Results from Simulation DRM1-v3 of the PS1 Design Reference Mission

Our current scheduler implementation is able to perform a nominal 39-month DRM survey. All the DRM surveys (or *programs*) are configured and three years of Haleakala weather data are injected into the simulation, and the results are promising.

The scheduler simulation running time depends of course on simulation time and number of active fields within the simulation at any one time. Currently it takes about eight hours to simulate one year of scheduling. Various optimization strategies have been discussed with the scheduler team at LSST but there are no magic bullets yet that can reduce this number significantly.

Figures 26 and 27 show 3pi survey and sweetspot survey coverage of the scheduler for observing cycle 89.

9.1 Total Scheduling Performance

Tables 16 and 17 summarize fundamental scheduler performance for our 39-month DRM survey. Each line of Table 17 represents the total performance of a single scheduler proposal. Each proposal name is prefixed with its scheduling program, e.g. 3pi, MD, etc.

Figure 27 Sweetspot survey coverage for observing cycle 89 (01-3piR-2007 through 30-3piR-2007).

Table 16. Overall Scheduling Efficiency

Parameter	Value		
Simulation Name	DRM1_v3		
Simulation Start Date	MJD 54016.00000	07 OCT 2006	
Simulation End Date	MJD 55202.18000	05 JAN 2010	
Simulation Run Time	1186.18000 days		
Exposure Time	20 254 134.00 sec	5626.15h	4.74h/day
Slew Time	5 210 626.73 sec	1447.40h	1.22h/day
Survey Time	25 464 760.73 sec	7073.54h	5.96h/day
Idle Time	12 038 400.00 sec	3344.00h	2.82h/day
Clear Time	37 503 160.73 sec	10417.54h	8.78h/day
Weather Loss	10 391 700.00 sec	2886.58h	2.43h/day
Night Time	47 894 860.73 sec	13304.13h	11.22h/day

Table 17. Individual Program-Filter Efficiencies

Name	Fields	Exp(hr)	Overhead(hr)	Total(hr)	Ovr(%)	Surv(%)	Exp/Clear(%)	(Exp+Ovr)/Clear(%)	SPEC(%)	PHOT(%)
MD-g	2065	137.67	13.21	150.87	91.25%	2.13%	1.32%	1.45%	1.95%	1.26%
MD-r	1939	129.27	7.45	136.72	94.55%	1.93%	1.24%	1.31%	1.83%	1.26%
MD-i	4216	281.07	16.16	297.23	94.56%	4.20%	2.70%	2.85%	3.97%	2.63%
MD-z	3415	227.67	13.74	241.40	94.31%	3.41%	2.19%	2.32%	3.22%	2.12%
MD-y	3387	225.80	11.87	237.67	95.01%	3.36%	2.17%	2.28%	3.19%	2.09%
CAL-r	3054	25.45	26.05	51.50	49.42%	0.73%	0.24%	0.49%	0.36%	0.36%
CAL-i	925	7.71	6.37	14.08	54.74%	0.20%	0.07%	0.14%	0.11%	0.11%
CAL-z	2062	17.18	18.43	35.61	48.25%	0.50%	0.16%	0.34%	0.24%	0.24%
CAL-y	931	7.76	6.65	14.41	53.84%	0.20%	0.07%	0.14%	0.11%	0.11%
CAL-g	1036	8.63	7.94	16.57	52.10%	0.23%	0.08%	0.16%	0.12%	0.12%
3pi-g	77744	1295.73	243.01	1538.74	84.21%	21.75%	12.44%	14.77%	18.32%	12.65%
3pi-r	78128	824.68	232.27	1056.95	78.02%	14.94%	7.92%	10.15%	11.66%	8.19%
3pi-i	76674	638.95	224.79	863.74	73.97%	12.21%	6.13%	8.29%	9.03%	6.10%
3pi-y	76797	639.98	234.99	874.97	73.14%	12.37%	6.14%	8.40%	9.05%	6.11%
3pi-z	75921	632.67	228.83	861.50	73.44%	12.18%	6.07%	8.27%	8.94%	6.24%
SS-r	49825	525.93	155.65	681.58	77.16%	9.64%	5.05%	6.54%	7.44%	5.14%
Total	458119	5626.15	1447.40	7073.54	79.54%	100.00%	54.01%	67.90%	79.54%	54.73%

From these tables we see that the overhead due to slews and readtime is about a 20%. Also notable is the average 2.88 hours/day of idle time that is not being scheduled properly. Most of this time is missing the full-moon time, and the current scheduler does not yet handle time around full moon optimally for lunation-based proposals. Finally, we see that total clear (observable) time is about 3/4 of the night time. This is based on the interpretation of the cloud camera data, i.e. that when the cloud camera shows 3/5 of the sky clear that it is truly useable. We do not have a good calibration of what the cloud camera indicates is "clear" versus truly photometric conditions.

Figure 28 and Figure 29 show examples of how the scheduler has coped with the details of scheduling around the historical weather stream.

Figure 30 and Figure 31 show all sky maps of the 3pi survey completion of a total of one year (six lunations on two pages). one lunation in each sky map. If a field is colored, the TTI pair was completed in that lunation. Orange indicates the observed z band parallax strip, yellow is the y band strip, and red in this case means all pairs of all three colors, g,r, and i. were completed. The lunations are ordered left to right per page, and then on to the next row. Note that the completion is poor in lunation 8 and 11, and 12. The color by color pair completion is plotted as a line graph in

Figure 28 Example of results of simulation for scheduling of individual nights. These are night 58, 59, and 62 of the mission, showing a range of how the scheduler coped with the weather. The solid thin line indicates the opacity from the cloud detector. If the line has three possible levels, LOW, indicating clear or "photometric" sky, MEDIUM, or partly cloudy (at least 3/5 of sky is clear), and HIGH, which means overcast. Plotted simultaneously as small triangles is the humidity. If the humidity exceeds 90 percent the Observatory closes and stays closed until the humidity has been below 90 percent for one half hour. Along the top, color coded are the observations and programs and filters scheduled. Black is No Observing, Grey is Idle, which means the scheduler could not figure out what to do: its ability to schedule anything was overconstrained,

Figure 29 More individual nights. Nights 63, 64, and 65 of the simulation. Same caption as Figure 28.

Figure 30 3pi pair completion. Six Observing Cycles (lunations)

Figure 31 3pi pair completion. Six Observing Cycles (lunations)

9.2 3pi and Sweetspots

Figure 32 shows a graph of 3pi and Sweetspot survey pair completion, or the percentage of attempted and completed TTI pairs each observing cycle. Figure ?? shows a graph of 3pi and Sweetspot survey triplet completion, or percentage of triplets attempted and completed in the g, r, i opposition fields each observing cycle. The downward spikes in the graphs indicate observing cycles in which there were heavy observing losses due to weather.

9.3 Medium-Deep/STS/M31

In this initial implementation of the simulation of the PS1 Surveys, M31 was simply treated as another medium deep field, and STS was treated as two Medium Deep Fields. Their individual cadences were not accurately simulated, but the total accumulated time is representative of what could be obtained for both of these programs.

Figure 32 3pi and Sweetspot TTI pair completion.

Table 18. Medium-Deep/STS/M31 Summary

Field/Filter	Number of Exposures	Total Exposure Time (hr)
XMM-LSS-DXS		
g	204	13.60h
r	198	13.20h
i	440	29.33h
z	306	20.40h
y	325	21.67h
CDFSGOODS/GEMS		
g	144	9.60h
r	141	9.40h
i	342	22.80h
z	264	17.60h
y	240	16.00h
IFA/Lynx		
g	172	11.47h
r	165	11.00h
i	302	20.13h
z	240	16.00h
y	250	16.67h
COSMOS		
g	150	10.00h
r	144	9.60h
i	233	15.53h
z	207	13.80h
y	204	13.60h
Lockman-DXS		
g	142	9.47h
r	135	9.00h
i	235	15.67h
z	214	14.27h
y	186	12.40h
NGC4258		
g	120	8.00h
r	120	8.00h
i	238	15.87h
z	260	17.33h
y	204	13.60h
VISTA-Video1		
g	128	8.53h
r	116	7.73h
i	249	16.60h
z	231	15.40h
y	228	15.20h
EliasN1-DXS		
g	151	10.07h
r	139	9.27h
i	308	20.53h
z	288	19.20h
y	252	16.80h
Vimos4-DXS		
g	163	10.87h
r	152	10.13h
i	397	26.47h
z	270	18.00h
y	304	20.27h
DEEP2		
g	159	10.60h
r	146	9.73h
i	360	24.00h

Table 18—Continued

Field/Filter	Number of Exposures	Total Exposure Time (hr)
z	235	15.67h
y	303	20.20h
M31		
r	1363	90.86h
STS		
i	2555	170.34h

Table 18 summarizes the coverage of the Medium-Deep/STS/M31 fields over the 39-month DRM survey.

9.4 Fidelity of the Scheduler

One issue is how well is the telescope slews and overheads properly being accounted for by the PS1 Scheduler. The test of this was to use a scheduled observations from the scheduler as input to the January 2007 ISP survey on the PS1 telescope. The scheduler has an apriori list of times for observations, but the schedule was formatted as a queue, and the telescope and ISP camera were commanded by the queue. The question is how well did the schedulers "clear" performance match reality of the real telescope?. Interestingly the real telescope would fall 10's of minutes behind the schedule, but nearly always caught back up, so that at the end of the 4 nights of ISP survey, the results on the real telescope were within a few minutes of the the total scheduled performance. Some of this is likely due to improper modeling of the rotator wrap, that averages out in the end. Further studies will be done during commissioning.

9.5 Summary of Scheduler Performance

The simulation shows that the surveys as scheduled were incomplete. However the simulation also has significant idle time. The amount of time missed due to weather is approximately the same as that which was currently idle time. The conclusion is that it is plausible that that the PS1 Surveys could be completed on time if: (i) they were properly scheduled, which at the moment means human intervention into the scheduling process with the OTIS observing tools, and (ii) if there is no significant time lost to engineering or other unanticipated down time, (iii) the historical weather stream is indicative of the weather through the PS1 Science Mission.

10 Future Development of the PS1 Scheduler

There is additional software design required to convert the current schedule simulator into a production tool that can schedule the real telescope.

10.1 Known Issues

The current prototype implementation of the DRM schedule does not yet satisfy DRM requirements. There are excesses of idle time, especially around full moon, that can be used to make up lost fields. Some efficiency is lost due to poor selection of the first field of a TTI pair. Observing windows for the 3pi proposals can be adjusted so that there is less competition between proposals; in other words, we can adjust the windows to spread the windows more evenly over an observing cycle.

10.2 Excess Idle Time

Currently all proposals are sensitive to a MaxMoonBrightness parameter that limits how bright the moon can be when observing. Due to the way start-of-lunation is computed in the scheduler code, it is not possible yet to set this value near 100%. The net result is that there are about four consecutive days of idle time around a full moon, even though the telescope is able to observe in some filters. Thus we know we can achieve significant gains in pair and triplet coverage by using this time. The correction for this problem is straightforward but has not been implemented yet.

There is additional available idle time toward the end of an observing cycle, when all observing windows for the 3pi proposals have expired. Minor adjustment of the observing windows can allow the scheduler to use this time, increasing pair and triplet efficiency.

10.3 Look-Ahead

Pair scheduling efficiency is the ability of the scheduler to make intelligent decisions regarding the scheduling of TTI-separated pairs of observations. At times the scheduler makes poor decisions in this regard, scheduling the first of a pair when the second would not be visible. The solution to this problem is to build in some look-ahead so that it is known prior to scheduling the first observation of a pair that the second will also be visible.

10.4 Baseline Schedule

Once the known software issues describe above have been corrected, it will be necessary to implement a baseline schedule that contains nightly average losses due to weather. This baseline schedule will provide a continuous approximate target of progress that the actual schedule (the schedule created based on real weather and other considerations) should meet.

The scheduler software design will need to support the existence of this baseline schedule and implement a goal-seeking function that given current weather inputs and past schedule, can optimize toward baseline goals.

10.5 Restartability

The current scheduler is not interruptible. If stopped, it is necessary to re-run a simulation completely. This of course is completely at odds with requirements for a production tool, so the scheduler code must be able to maintain state so that it can be stopped and restarted after some arbitrary time interval.

10.6 Real time Scheduling, Observing Tools, and Queue Operation

10.7 Engineering Requirements

The vast amount of engineering metadata together with astronomical data within the summit (OTIS) database obtained during the normal survey observations will enable identification of many engineering issues and observing strategies (e.g. best venting to get best seeing under given wind conditions). If the project is allowed to, on rare occasion, degrade the image quality, then such a strategy will reduce much of the need for scheduled engineering time.

Any other engineering time will come from the generally allocation as if it were weather.

10.8 Mitigation Strategy for Lost Observing Time

Time lost for any reason means some part of the scheduled surveys will not get done. If it becomes necessary to drop scheduled observations due to time lost, whatever the reason, the observations removed from the scheduling queue will be, in order of first removal:

10.8.1 3π Survey in g band, starting from the celestial pole and in decreasing declination to 70 degrees.

10.8.2 3π Survey in y band, starting from the celestial pole and in decreasing declination to 70 degrees.

10.8.3 3π Survey in z band, starting from the celestial pole and in decreasing declination to 70 degrees.

10.8.4 3π Survey in r band, starting from the celestial pole and in decreasing declination to 70 degrees.

The i band will be maintained across the pole to close the primary astrometric solution.

If this mitigation strategy is insufficient to make up for the lost time, the PS1SC Board will decide from a selection of proposals made by the PS1 Project Scientist.

10.9 Release of Future Simulations of the PS1 DRM

With the future development of the PS1 Scheduler and Observing occurring on a rapid time scale, it is anticipated that future releases of simulations of the PS1 DRM will be made available, culminating in a revised version of this Design Reference Mission when the performance issues of the Observatory, Telescope, Camera, and IPP are better known from commissioning runs.

11 Data Products, Management, and Access during the PS1 Science Mission

Transient Catalogs and Detrended Image Data will be available over the internet to a US mainland site on a close to real time basis with less than an hour latency for much of the mission.

Details regarding all data transfer issues will be released in an upcoming white paper. For urgent issues contact Pui Hin Rhoads, phr@ifa.hawaii.edu for data transfer issues.

12 Public Data Release

The PS1 Science Consortium has agreed to allow the release of all PS1 Data Products, including image data, signal to noise maps, catalog data, derived data products and metadata to the astronomical community and public at large. There is no commitment by the PS1SC to fund any means of serving PS1 Data Products. The expectation is that the data will be of sufficient value that either finding a source to fund the distribution of PS1 Data Products or providing the PS1 Data Products to other institutions or organizations whose mission includes serving astronomical data will be sufficient to address this issue.

Table 19. PS1 Medium Deep Fields

No.	Name	Alt Name	RA (J2000)	Dec(J2000)	Comment
01	PS1 MD01	XMM-LSS-DXS	02 22 24	-04 30 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
02	PS1 MD02	CDFS/GOODS/GEMS	03 32 24	-27 48 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
03	PS1 MD03	IFA/Lynx	08 43 00	+44 40 00	Radio Survey Field
04	PS1 MD04	COSMOS	10 00 00	+02 12 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
05	PS1 MD05	Lockman-DXS	11 00 00	+57 00 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
06	PS1 MD06	NGC 4258	12 18 57	+47 18 14	H ₂ O Maser - geometric distance
07	PS1 MD07	VISTA-Video1	14 00 00	+05 00 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
08	PS1 MD08	EliasN1-DXS	16 00 00	+57 00 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
09	PS1 MD09	Vimos4-DXS-SSA	22 00 00	+00 30 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
10	PS1 MD10	DEEP2	23 30 00	+00 00 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field

13 Outreach

The PS1 Operations Budget has no funding for Outreach, nonetheless it is expected that PS1SC scientists with an interest in Public Outreach will contribute time and conceivably search for funding for Outreach efforts to make PS1 results accessible and comprehensible to K-12 students and the general public. Each institutional member of the PS1SC is committed to Outreach, and it is expected will contribute some portion of its Outreach efforts to make PS1 results available to the broadest possible community.

14 Acknowledgements

PS1 publications, refereed or not, must include the following statement as acknowledgement:

”The PS1 Surveys have been made possible through contributions of the Institute for Astronomy, the University of Hawai’i, the Pan-STARRS Project Office, the Max-Planck Society and its participating institutes, the Max Planck Institute for Astronomy, Heidelberg and the Max Planck Institute for Extraterrestrial Physics, Garching, The Johns Hopkins University, the University of Durham; the University of Edinburgh, the Queen’s University Belfast, the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics, the Los Cumbres Observatory Global Telescope Network, Incorporated, and the National Central University of Taiwan.”

The Pan-STARRS project includes contributions from The Institute for Astronomy, the Maui High Performance Computing Center, SAIC, AFRL, and Lincoln Laboratory.

15 Appendix A: Table of PS1 Medium Deep Fields

Table 19 lists the *approximate* centers 10 PS1 Medium Deep Fields. Final boresight pointing to be determined by bright star distribution, and foreground galaxy inclusion. Four of the MD fields are northern fields, but none have a Declination greater than 57 degrees. Six are accessible from southern telescopes.

Table 20. PS1 Deep M31 Survey and Stellar Transit Survey Fields

No.	Name	Alt Name	RA (J2000)	Dec(J2000)	Comment
11	PS1 M31	Andromeda	00 42 42	+41 16 00	Deep Survey of M31
12	PS1 STS1	Outskirts of Bulge	19 50 48	+17 03 39	3 footprints STS Campaign 1
26	PS1 STS2	Hyades	00 40 00	+15 00 00	4 footprints, STS Campaign 2
27	PS1 STS3	Praesepe	08 30 00	+20 00 00	4 footprints, STS Campaign 3

Table 21. PS1 Calibration Fields

No.	Name	Alt Name	RA (J2000)	Dec(J2000)	Comment
13	North Pole		00 00 00	+90 00 00	Always accessible
14	SA92		00 55 08	+00 42 32	Dense Landolt Std Field
15	Perseus Cluster	Abell 426	03 19 00	+41 33 00	Center of Perseus Cluster
16	SA95		03 55 05	+00 17 38	Dense Landolt Std Field
17	Taurus dark cloud		04 30 00	+25 00 00	Diverse extinction
18	SA98		06 52 07	+00 17 10	Dense Landolt Std Field
19	M81-M82-HolmIX		09 56 40	+69 22 00	Local Group
20	Virgo		12 30 00	+13 00 00	Center of Virgo Cluster
21	Hercules Cluster		16 05 08	+17 45 28	Center of Hercules Cluster
22	M17-M24 region		18 14 00	-19 30 00	Numerous star clusters and nebulae
23	SA110		18 42 07	+00 05 44	Dense Landolt Std Field
24	Kepler		19 22 40	+44 30 00	Kepler Mission astrometric field
25	3C454.1		22 50 33	+71 29 19	Northern Field

16 Appendix B: PS1 STS and M31 Survey Fields

The PS1 Science Mission Stellar Transit Survey and Deep M31 Survey Fields are listed below in Table 20. The STS fields are expected to take three campaigns, only the first is listed here.

17 Appendix C: Table of PS1 Calibration Fields

The Calibration fields listed in Table 21 are in addition to the Medium Fields, M31, and the Stellar Transit Survey fields, all of which serve as a calibration field for their part of the Sky. Calibration type exposures will be taken on each of these when they are being used as Calibration fields. Table 21 list the *approximate* centers of the 10 PS1 Calibration Fields. Final boresight pointing to be determined by bright star distribution, and foreground

Thus there are 25 reasonably well spaced fields across the 3π sky for regular photometric calibration. Any PS1 field can serve as a calibration field, i.e. it will have enough stellar sources to measure relative photometry.

The complete set of all PS1 photometric and astrometric calibration fields from the combination of the MD, M31, STS, and Cal fields are given in Table 22.

The distribution of Medium Deep, Calibration, M31 and STS fields are shown in Figure 33.

Table 22. Complete set of PS1 Astrometric and Photometric Calibration Fields

No.	Name	Alt Name	Survey	RA (J2000)	Dec(J2000)	Comment
13	North Pole		Cal	00 00 00	+90 00 00	Always accessible
11	M31	Andromeda	M31	00 42 42	+41 16 00	Deep Survey of M31
14	SA92		Cal	00 55 08	+00 42 32	Dense Landolt Field
01	PS1 MD01	XMM-LSS-DXS	MD	02 22 24	-04 30 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
15	Perseus Cluster	Abell 426	Cal	03 19 00	+41 33 00	Center of Perseus Cluster
02	PS1 MD02	CDFS/GOODS/GEMS	MD	03 32 24	-27 48 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
16	SA95		Cal	03 55 05	+00 17 38	Dense Landolt Field
17	Taurus dark cloud		Cal	04 30 00	+25 00 00	Diverse extinction, Dark Sky
18	SA98		Cal	06 52 07	+00 17 10	Dense Landolt Field
03	PS1 MD03	IFA/Lynx	MD	08 43 00	+44 40 00	Radio Survey Field
19	M81-M82-HolmIX		Cal	09 56 40	+69 22 00	Local Group
04	PS1 MD04	COSMOS	MD	10 00 00	+02 12 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
05	PS1 MD05	Lockman-DXS	MD	11 00 00	+57 00 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
06	PS1 MD06	NGC 4258	MD	12 18 57	+47 18 14	H ₂ O Maser - geometric distance
20	Virgo		Cal	12 30 00	+13 00 00	Center of Virgo Cluster
07	PS1 MD07	VISTA-Video1	MD	14 00 00	+05 00 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
08	PS1 MD08	EliasN1-DXS	MD	16 00 00	+57 00 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
21	Hercules Cluster		Cal	16 05 08	+17 45 28	Center of Hercules Cluster
22	M17-M24 region		Cal	18 14 00	-19 30 00	numerous star clusters and nebulae
23	SA110		Cal	18 42 07	+00 05 44	Dense Landolt Field
24	Kepler Field		Cal	19 22 40	+44 30 00	Kepler Mission astrometric field
12	PS1 STS1		STS	19 50 48	+17 03 39	3 footprints, STS Campaign 1
09	PS1 MD09	Vimos4-DXS-SSA	MD	22 00 00	+00 30 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field
25	3C454.1		Cal	22 50 33	+71 29 19	Northern Field
10	PS1 MD10	DEEP2	MD	23 30 00	+00 00 00	Multi-wavelength Survey Field

Figure 33 Position of all special fields to be used as Calibration fields. Red, Medium Deep Survey Fields, Black Calibration Fields, Orange, M31, Blue, STS Campaign 1.

18 Appendix D: Table of data sets to be provided on the web

Note, the sensitivity estimates in this table come from a small Barr filter, not the large PS1 GPC1 Barr filter set. The calculations should be redone with measured curves for the large PS1 filters. These files are on ps1sc.org under documents.

- Nominal 75 micron thick Q.E. curve
- Measured PS1 Filter Set data
- Nominal aluminum reflectivity (M1, used for M2 calculations)
- Nominal atmospheric transmission curve
- Nominal airglow spectrum
- Estimated throughput per bandpass
- Estimated sensitivity per bandpass
- PS1 Optics Zeemax file and scripts for spot diagrams
- Shutter velocity profile
- Tabulation of merged weather stream

19 Appendix E: RF Units and Conversions

The relevant RF units and conversions for interpreting spectrum analyzer data are as follows: Decibel conversion of Power in milliWatts,

$$dBm = 10/\log[\text{Signal}(mW/1mW)]$$

Conversion of Power to Voltage

$$dBmV = dBm + 107$$

Where the constant 107 comes from $P = V^2/R$, or $V = (PR)^{0.5} = 0.23V = 223000mV$ for a resistance of 50W and a power of 1 mW hence $20\text{Log}_{10}[223000mV] = 107dB$. The Electric Field strength at the antenna is

$$E_{dB} = AF_{dB} + Vr_{dB}$$

where AF_{dB} is the Antenna Factor in dB/M, E_{dB} is the Field strength at the antenna in $dB\mu V/M$ and Vr_{dB} is the output voltage from receiving antenna in $dB\mu V$. Then the relation of the Electric field to Power Density is

$$dBmV/M = dBm/M^2 + 115.8$$

where the constant 115.8 comes from $P = |E|^2/Z_0$ where Z_0 is the impedance of free space.

20 Appendix F: Acronyms

CA - Cooperative Agreement

CAM - Gigapixel Camera Group

IPP - Image Processing Pipeline

GPC1 - Gigapixel Camera #1

LCC - Lower Cassigrain Core

M1 - Primary Mirror, aluminum coated

M2 - Secondary Mirror

M2x - Unacceptable Secondary Mirror

M2a - protected silver coated secondary mirror

MOID - Minimum Orbital Intersection Distance

MOA - Memorandum of Agreement

MOPS - Moving Object Processing System

MPG - Max Planck Gesellschaft (Max Planck Society)

ORR - Operational Readiness Review

OTIS - Observatory, Telescope, & Instrument Software

Pan-STARRS - Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System

PHO - Potentially Hazardous Objects

PI - Principal Investigator

PS1 - Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System Telescope #1

PS1SC - PS1 Science Consortium

PS4 - Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System Telescope #4

PSPS - Published Science Products System (database)

RRR - Restricted Rotator Range

TBR - To Be Reviewed

TC3 - Test Camera #3

TEL - PS1 Telescope Group

TTI - Transient Time Interval

UCC - Upper Cassigrain Core